

**D2.4 - BIOECONOMY ASSESSMENT AND
MONITORING FRAMEWORK AND DESCRIPTION OF
DASHBOARD**

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SUSTRACK project aims to accelerate the transition towards a sustainable, circular, and bio-based economy in Europe by identifying enabling conditions, addressing systemic barriers, and supporting evidence-based policymaking. Within this framework, **WP2** focused on developing a robust approach to monitor the progress of the European bioeconomy through the **SUSTRACK Bioeconomy Monitoring Framework** and its operational implementation in the **SUSTRACK Monitoring Tool**.

The bioeconomy plays a central role in achieving the EU's long-term sustainability goals, notably climate neutrality by 2050, circular resource use, and the regeneration of ecosystems. Yet, monitoring progress remains a major challenge due to the fragmented and heterogeneous nature of existing data. The **SUSTRACK monitoring framework** was designed to complement the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS) by providing a more operational, user-friendly, and policy-relevant tool to benchmark national bioeconomy performance across EU Member States.

The framework builds on the five societal objectives of the 2018 EU Bioeconomy Strategy, linking them conceptually to the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**. This alignment ensures that the monitoring system not only tracks economic performance but also assesses environmental and social dimensions. Over 500 indicators were reviewed and classified according to sustainability pillars, policy relevance, and data availability. A systematic prioritisation based on SMART criteria led to the selection of a concise set of **headline indicators**, grouped into three key areas:

1. **Sustainable resource management**
2. **Environmental performance**
3. **Competitiveness and jobs**

Indicators were normalised and converted into standardised scores (1-6), allowing for comparability across countries and thematic areas. The **interactive SUSTRACK monitoring tool** enables users to perform benchmarking analyses, visualise country profiles, and conduct hotspot analyses through a dynamic interface.

To further synthesise results, a **cluster analysis** was performed to group countries with similar performance profiles. This revealed meaningful patterns: countries like Belgium, the Netherlands, and Finland act as consistent leaders across dimensions, while others display asymmetric progress, for instance, strong environmental results not yet matched by competitiveness gains (Spain, Italy), or strong economic performance paired with weaker resource management (Cyprus, Malta). These insights highlight where policy interventions can create convergence and foster win-win outcomes across sustainability dimensions.

Overall, the SUSTRACK monitoring framework demonstrates how a simplified, yet conceptually grounded approach can make bioeconomy assessment more accessible and actionable. The

resulting tool provides an intuitive entry point for countries at different stages of bioeconomy development, particularly those without existing monitoring systems, helping them identify strengths, weaknesses, and policy priorities.

Looking ahead, the SUSTRACK monitoring system offers strong potential for **future exploitation and integration**. Its functionalities could inspire further evolution of the EU-BMS, particularly by incorporating benchmarking capabilities and dynamic linkages between indicators and the SDGs, thereby enhancing the coherence, usability, and policy impact of bioeconomy monitoring across Europe.

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List of Abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
CBBE	Circular Bio-Based Economy
CE	Circular Economy
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EU-BMS	EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System
GHG	Greenhouse-Gas emissions
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KCB	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SO	Societal Objectives

1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of achieving a net-zero emissions European economy by 2050 requires a fundamental shift from linear, fossil-based systems to circular, bio-based systems. This transition is essential not only for meeting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) but also for reconciling environmental protection with sustainable economic growth. However, this transformation is inherently complex, as it involves systemic societal changes, the adoption of cutting-edge technologies, and the engagement of multiple stakeholders. It calls for the establishment of a new societal and economic framework, as well as the alignment of policy priorities across various initiatives to ensure the integration of bioeconomy principles into all policy domains and foster coherence.

In this context, systematic monitoring of bioeconomy progress is a key priority for ensuring responsible and inclusive governance, as well as coherent and evidence-based policymaking. The 2018 update of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy explicitly recognises this need, calling for the development of comprehensive, reliable, and comparable information systems to support decision-making across sectors and governance levels. Monitoring systems, modelling techniques, and robust datasets are thus crucial tools for improving the understanding of the bioeconomy's complexity, assessing trade-offs, and identifying potential transition pathways.

At the European level, the EU Bioeconomy Strategy (European Commission, 2018) committed the European Commission to establishing an internationally coherent monitoring system to track economic, environmental, and social progress towards a sustainable and circular bioeconomy. The result of this commitment is the **EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS)**, developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) in cooperation with a broad range of stakeholders. Based on a conceptual framework (Robert et al., 2020), the EU-BMS translates the strategic objectives of the bioeconomy strategy into an operational vision for a sustainable EU bioeconomy. Released in 2020 and hosted within the **Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy (KCB)**¹, the EU-BMS offers a dashboard to explore key indicators and themes relevant to the bioeconomy and is updated regularly as new data becomes available.

However, the current landscape of national bioeconomy monitoring is uneven. Of the 11 Member States (MS) that have adopted a national bioeconomy strategy, only six—Germany, Finland, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, and Portugal—have included or implemented a monitoring system (Korosuo et al., 2024). This highlights a significant gap in the systematic tracking of bioeconomy progress across the EU. Furthermore, the EU-BMS, while offering a comprehensive and holistic framework, was primarily designed as a conceptual system rather than a fully operational, data-driven tool. Its complexity and abstract nature may limit its usability for practitioners and policymakers who require targeted assessments focused on specific countries or bioeconomy aspects.

In response to these challenges, the SUSTRACK project, and specifically T2.3, aims to contribute to bridging this gap by developing a complementary tool for country performance assessment. This report seeks to address this need by describing the SUSTRACK monitoring framework and the respective implementation of the interactive dashboard. This tool builds on the findings from stakeholder engagement, co-creation processes, and case study analyses carried out in SUSTRACK,

¹ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy_en

and it complements the EU-BMS by providing an easy approach to hotspot analysis in the bioeconomy transition.

1.1 Objective of the report

This report aims to present the SUSTRACK monitoring framework and its operationalisation through the SUSTRACK monitoring tool, developed as part of T2.3. The framework is intended to complement the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS) by offering a more targeted and operational tool for assessing country-level performance and supporting decision-making in the bioeconomy transition.

While the EU-BMS provides a comprehensive and conceptually rich foundation for monitoring bioeconomy progress at the EU level, its broad scope and technical details may pose challenges for stakeholders seeking more tailored insights at national levels. The SUSTRACK framework responds to this need by offering a more hands-on, data-driven tool that enables hotspot analysis, country benchmarking, and performance monitoring at the country level.

In addition to supporting performance assessments and benchmark analyses, the SUSTRACK tool also functions as a repository of existing knowledge on bioeconomy indicators relevant to monitoring. It includes more than 500 indicators organised under a structured taxonomy. This facilitates users' experience as they can use specific filters such as sustainability pillars, societal objectives, or implementation level to retrieve indicators of interest. Furthermore, the SUSTRACK monitoring framework explicitly links individual indicators to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), helping to highlight potential synergies and trade-offs depending on the nature of the relationship between indicators and specific SDG targets.

Ultimately, this report seeks to support evidence-based policymaking by providing a flexible and user-friendly monitoring tool that responds to the needs of stakeholders across the bioeconomy landscape. It describes the conceptual and technical components of the monitoring framework, the structure of the interactive dashboard, the methodology used for the benchmarking analysis, and the metadata associated with the selected indicators.

1.2 Structure of the report

The report is structured into six chapters. Following the **introduction and the objectives** of the report (Chapter 1), Chapter 2 presents the **SUSTRACK Circular Bioeconomy Framework**, which serves as the conceptual foundation of the SUSTRACK Monitoring System. This chapter explains how the framework builds on the objectives of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and highlights its alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). By doing so, it provides both a normative and policy-oriented perspective for monitoring the bioeconomy transition.

Chapter 3 introduces the **SUSTRACK Monitoring System** in detail. It begins by outlining the tool's objectives, followed by a structured presentation of the headline indicators, organised into three key areas: (i) sustainable and renewable resource use, (ii) environmental performance of the bioeconomy, and (iii) bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs. The chapter then presents the results of the bioeconomy transition assessment, including a cluster analysis that identifies patterns and divides across European regions. Section 3.4 describes the structure and functionalities of the monitoring system, while a practical **case study on Spain** demonstrates its application. The chapter concludes with the technical specifications of the tool.

Chapter 4 focuses on the **methodologies** underpinning the monitoring system. It details the approach used to prioritise headline indicators, conduct the country-level benchmarking analysis, and identify potential synergies and trade-offs between bioeconomy indicators and specific SDG targets. In addition, it explains the transformation of land use, land use change, and forestry (LULUCF) data into a distance-to-target score, ensuring comparability.

Chapter 5 provides **recommendations for future work**. It summarises the additional work carried out under T2.3, which, due to technical constraints, could not be fully integrated into the monitoring system. These aspects concern mainly conceptual gaps and persistent data limitations, particularly in indicators related to social aspects and environmental pollutants.

Finally, Chapter 6 offers **concluding reflections**, summarising the contributions of the SUSTRACK Monitoring Framework and highlighting its potential to inform evidence-based policy for a sustainable and inclusive circular bioeconomy.

2 SUSTRACK CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY FRAMEWORK

The SUSTRACK Circular Bioeconomy Framework has been conceptualised as a bridge between existing European policy strategies, operational monitoring tools, and the practical needs of policymakers. Its development builds on three main foundations: the EU Bioeconomy Strategy (which provides the theoretical orientation and societal objectives), the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS) (which offers operational foundations in terms of available indicators and data), and the identified “needs” of policymakers for a hands-on tool that can deliver quick, targeted insights into hotspots of the bioeconomy transition. This pragmatic dimension is particularly important, as the framework is intended not only to capture progress but also to support decision-making and highlight where specific policy actions are required.

The framework is also fully aligned with the SUSTRACK multi-layered working definition of the Circular Bio-based Economy (CBBE) developed in WP5 (see Figure 1). This conceptualisation places the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the outer loop, representing the overarching global goals to which the bioeconomy transition contributes. Moving inward, the next layer reflects the societal objectives of the CBBE, as established in the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, thereby grounding the framework in existing political consensus. Next layer exemplifies the principles of the Circular Economy (CE), as articulated in the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, providing a political and operational orientation for the CE.

Figure 1: SUSTRACK working definition of the Circular Bio-Based Economy (CBBE) (source: SUSTRACK D5.1)

Within SUSTRACK, CE principles are reinterpreted through the specific lens of the CBBE, reflecting both the opportunities and the constraints of a bio-based transition:

- **Reduction of GHG emissions** is not only understood as lowering emissions from production and consumption but also as recognising the climate relevance of biomass use. This requires accounting for emissions linked to biomass cultivation, land-use change, and the potential climate benefits of substituting fossil-based materials. SUSTRACK places particular emphasis on material substitution (e.g., plastics, construction, chemicals) rather than energy substitution, since the latter is already addressed by established climate and energy policies.
- **Resource use efficiency** becomes central to mitigating ecological pressures in a context of rising biomass demand. In the CBBE framework, efficiency is not merely a cost-saving mechanism but a way to ensure that biomass stocks are used wisely, through cascading, recycling, and valorisation of residues and by-products.
- **Decoupling resource use from economic growth** is interpreted as a critical safeguard against the risk that increasing efficiency or substituting fossil fuels with biomass still results in overexploitation of ecosystems. The CBBE lens highlights the risks of biodiversity loss, soil degradation, and dependency on critical raw materials, even in a bio-based system. Decoupling, therefore, underscores the importance of ensuring that scaling up bio-based production does not translate into new unsustainable pressures on natural capital.

Taken together, these reinterpretations show that while the CBBE is guided by the logic of circularity, its reliance on biological resources requires particular caution. It is not a panacea for all sustainability challenges but rather a targeted pathway that can meaningfully contribute to climate neutrality, sustainable resource use, and resilience, provided its principles are applied with attention to ecological limits and potential trade-offs.

In this way, the SUSTRACK Circular Bioeconomy Framework is not only a conceptual structure but also a practical tool that provides science-based evidence to support decision-making. Drawing

on robust data, it enables countries to assess their performance against key bioeconomy objectives and principles. The tool integrates a benchmarking dimension, showing whether a country is performing well or lagging behind in specific areas of the CBBE transition. At the same time, it highlights the indirect impacts on related SDGs, making explicit the synergies and trade-offs that emerge when pursuing bio-based and circular strategies.

2.1 Societal objectives of the EU bioeconomy and their link to the SDGs

The ambition of a sustainable bioeconomy is well articulated in the **2018 EU Bioeconomy Strategy**, which builds upon and significantly broadens the scope of the original 2012 Strategy. While the earlier approach was primarily focused on the development and growth of bio-based industries, the 2018 update introduced a more balanced and systemic vision. It defined **five overarching societal objectives (SO)** (Figure 2) that place the promotion of economic growth, social well-being, and environmental integrity on an equal footing. In this renewed vision, the health of ecosystems and the understanding of their ecological boundaries are no longer peripheral concerns but integral elements of a resilient and inclusive bioeconomy (European Commission: Joint Research Centre, 2020).

This evolution reflects a fundamental recognition: **economic prosperity ultimately depends on healthy and productive ecosystems**. Overexploitation of natural resources can undermine the very foundations of the economic and social systems that depend on them. This interdependence is particularly evident in the bioeconomy, whose sectors are inherently tied to renewable resources and biological processes. Unlike other parts of the economy, bio-based activities—from agriculture and forestry to bio-based manufacturing—interact directly and continuously with the biosphere.

Figure 2: The five objectives of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy

The EU bioeconomy is also **deeply intertwined with the United Nations 2030 Agenda and its 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**. Both frameworks share the ambition of achieving prosperity within planetary boundaries, yet their interactions are complex and multidimensional. While many bioeconomy actions create **positive synergies** with the SDGs, such as the promotion of sustainable resource use, renewable energy, or biodiversity conservation, they can also generate **trade-offs** when economic expansion exerts pressure on ecosystems or social equity.

Empirical studies show that environmental sustainability actions, particularly those associated with **SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation)**, **SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy)**, **SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities)**, **SDG 13 (Climate Action)**, and **SDGs 14 and 15 (Life Below Water and Life on Land)**, stand out as key enablers for achieving multiple goals across all

dimensions of sustainability (Ronzon & Sanjuán, 2020). In contrast, the picture is more mixed for the social and economic pillars. For example, indicators such as **value added** (economic dimension) and **employment in manufacturing** (social dimension) often reveal potential trade-offs. These interlinkages highlight the importance of adopting a **systems perspective**, acknowledging that the bioeconomy can drive progress towards several SDGs but also needs careful governance to avoid shifting pressures from one domain to another.

Both the **societal objectives** of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and the **SDGs** have been central to the development of the **SUSTRACK monitoring framework**. The societal objectives have guided the **structure of the dashboard** and the **classification of indicators**, ensuring alignment with the EU's strategic vision. At the same time, each indicator has been **mapped against relevant SDGs**, assessing whether it contributes to or potentially weakens specific goals. This dual alignment provides a coherent foundation for understanding how bioeconomy transitions can simultaneously support European policy priorities and global sustainability targets.

3 METHODS

This section explains the several methods used to design the SUSTRACK monitoring system and convey the information, data used in the benchmark analysis, as well as the approach used to visualise the hotspot mapping of Indicators vs SDGs. Namely, we worked on three different methodological strands:

1. Country-performance benchmarking methodology
2. Working a distance-to-target metrics for LULUCS emissions
3. Mapping indicators - SDGs relationships

These are further elaborated in the following sections.

3.1 Country-performance benchmarking methodology

To support countries in conducting self-assessments of their progress towards a sustainable bioeconomy, a structured methodological pathway was designed. This approach ensures that the monitoring system is both analytically robust and policy-relevant. The process evolved through a sequence of steps, from indicator identification to thematic grouping and scoring (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Overview of the benchmarking methodology

3.1.1 Step 1: Identification of candidate indicators

The process began with the comprehensive identification of potential indicators. The primary source was the Joint Research Centre's (JRC) database developed for the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS), the most extensive initiative currently tracking bioeconomy progress in Europe. Additional sources included Eurostat, FAO, and complementary datasets. In total, 242 candidate indicators were identified.

3.1.2 Step 2: Review through SMART criteria

Each indicator was reviewed according to the SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Traceable). A two-stage cut-off process was applied:

1. Measurable, Traceable, and Time-Relevant Indicators

Indicators were retained if they met the following conditions:

- **Time relevance:** To capture recent trends, data prior to 2016 were excluded ².
- **Availability:** Reliable data available for at least 50% of the years between 2016 and 2022, ensuring temporal consistency and territorial representativeness. Indicators with coverage limited to a small number of countries were excluded.

² During the initial period of T2.3 the time relevance was set to be 2015-2021. However, as new data became available towards the end of the project the time-set was updated as 2016-2022.

- **Traceability:** data had to come from trusted and official sources (e.g., JRC, Eurostat, FAO), reinforcing credibility and comparability.

This refinement reduced the list from 224 to 157 indicators.

2. Relevance to SUSTRACK Scope

To ensure alignment with SUSTRACK's objectives, additional criteria were applied:

- **Geographical scope:** Indicators relating to non-EU countries were discarded.
- **Sectoral coherence:** Food supply and food security indicators were excluded, as these were not part of SUSTRACK's sectoral focus (construction, textile, plastic, chemical).
- **Policy relevance:** Indicators representing unmanaged environmental stocks (e.g., terrestrial or marine areas) were removed, since they provide limited actionable insights for policymakers.

This second filter reduced the set from 157 to 143 indicators.

3.1.3 Step 3: Prioritisation through “easiness of interpretation”

The third step focused on ensuring that indicators were **interpretable** and could support **meaningful comparisons** across countries and time. This required assessing two complementary aspects:

1. **Directional clarity:** indicators had to provide an unambiguous signal of progress or decline in the circular bioeconomy transition. This avoids misleading results and makes communication to policymakers and stakeholders more straightforward.
2. **Comparability through normalisation:** Indicators had to be expressible in a way that allowed benchmarking across different contexts. Without a meaningful denominator or reference base, absolute values risk misinterpretation.

Examples of retained indicators:

- **Circular material use rate:** An increase unambiguously signals more efficient use of resources and reduced pressure on virgin materials.
- **Biomass waste generation:** A decrease clearly reflects reduced inefficiencies and environmental pressure.

Examples of excluded indicators due to directional ambiguity:

- **Farming intensification:** While potentially positive for yields, it is often linked to negative impacts such as soil degradation and biodiversity loss. Because the net effect depends on context, it cannot serve as a straightforward benchmark indicator.

Examples of excluded indicators due to lack of comparability:

- **Volume of Roundwood Removals (m³):** In absolute terms, this number says little about sustainability. Its meaning depends on the size and condition of the underlying forest stock. Without a denominator (e.g., removals relative to available stock or regeneration rate), it cannot support fair benchmarking across countries.

By removing such indicators, the framework avoided two key risks:

- **Misinterpretation** (when changes could be both positive and negative depending on context).

- **Misleading comparisons** (when absolute values are not normalised and therefore not comparable).

This refinement reduced the number of indicators from 143 to 112, ensuring that the retained indicators are **clear in meaning, comparable across contexts, and robust enough to support benchmarking and hotspot analysis.**

3.1.4 Step 4: Identification of additional indicators

While the EU-BMS provided the backbone of the indicator set, it did not fully utilise all the existing data for monitoring the circular bioeconomy transition. Therefore, a complementary step was undertaken to explore and include additional indicators based on consortium expertise and external data sources. Additional indicators identified and included:

- **Resource Productivity:** Retrieved directly from Eurostat, this indicator is a cornerstone of the EU Circular Economy Monitoring Framework and a widely recognised measure of resource efficiency. It provides a link between resource use and economic performance, reflecting progress in decoupling growth from material consumption.
- **GHG Emissions in Bio-Based Sectors:** Using Eurostat's dataset `env_ac_ainah_r2`, sectoral greenhouse gas emissions were retrieved for bio-based activities. To ensure comparability and benchmarking, bio-based GHG emissions were estimated for hybrid sectors (e.g., textiles, chemicals) by weighting total sectoral emissions with the bio-based Gross Value Added (GVA) share, as provided by the Data-Modelling platform of resource economics³ (Lasarte López et al., 2022).
- **Emission Intensities (g CO₂ per Euro):** Retrieved from Eurostat's `env_ac_aeint_r2`, this indicator provides an intensity-based perspective, complementing absolute emissions. Similar to the absolute GHG emissions, bio-based intensities for hybrid sectors were estimated by applying bio-based GVA weights.

Other indicators explored but not included:

- **Monetisation of Externalities:** We investigated the possibility of incorporating external cost data related to environmental and health damages. However, we have identified available data (country-level externalities) only for a single year, limiting their usability for benchmarking or trend analysis.
- **Waste Generation and Pollutant Releases (PRTR):** Data from the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (PRTR) were also explored, including emissions and waste disaggregated by industrial activities. However, pollutants and waste were classified according to economic activities not directly reconcilable with the bioeconomy. This made it virtually impossible to isolate how much of a given pollutant or waste stream could be attributed to bio-based versus non-bio-based sectors.

For these reasons, we ultimately decided to exclude these datasets from the monitoring system. Nevertheless, they remain relevant and promising areas for future research and methodological development (see Limitations and Recommendations for Further Work chapter).

This step increased the number of indicators from 112 to 134, as emissions and emissions intensities were provided in total terms and by - ten - different sectors for both indicators.

³ <https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/mashup/BIOECONOMICS/>

3.1.5 Step 5: Normalisation

The final step in the benchmarking preparation process involved ensuring that all selected indicators were expressed in a manner that allows for meaningful comparison across countries and over time. This step was crucial to avoid distortions linked to country size, economic scale, or sectoral structure, and to ensure that the benchmarking results reflect true performance differences rather than scale effects.

The normalisation process involved the following actions:

- **Expression in relative terms:** Each indicator was double-checked to ensure it was expressed in a **comparable and relative form**. This included:
 - **Per capita terms**, e.g., food waste was systematically expressed as kilograms per person to allow fair comparison across Member States.
 - **Per unit of economic activity**, e.g., gross value added (GVA) per person employed in bioeconomy sectors. Indicators expressed in absolute monetary terms, such as total GVA per sector, were removed to prevent size-related distortions.
 - **Percentage shares or intensities**, e.g., GHG emissions per euro of output or the share of renewables in energy consumption.
- **Elimination of redundancies:** During this step, redundant indicators that overlapped in meaning with other, more representative metrics were excluded. For instance:
 - **Turnover** was excluded as it largely overlaps with GVA, which was retained as the more meaningful measure of value creation.
 - Absolute measures of **sectoral GVA** were excluded, retaining only **per employee versions** to better capture productivity and comparability.
 - For **GHG emissions**, both per capita values and intensities (g per euro) were initially considered. However, since the two provided highly similar country rankings, we decided to retain only **GHG intensities** for the benchmarking analysis, as they better capture the efficiency dimension of bio-based production.
- **Special treatment of LULUCF emissions:** Particular care was given to **GHG emissions and removals from Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF)**. Unlike other indicators, these cannot be directly compared across countries due to the **existence of national 2030 targets** based on territorial configurations (e.g., forest cover, land use structure). Standard per-capita or per-GDP normalisation would not capture these differences. To address this, an **ad-hoc normalisation method** was applied, benchmarking each country against its **specific 2030 LULUCF target**. This ensured fairness and comparability. The details of this procedure are provided in *Chapter 4.3*.

Through this step, the indicators set was reduced to 39 indicators.

3.1.6 Step 6: Transformation of indicators into scores

To make the results of the benchmarking analysis **comparable and interpretable across countries and indicators**, all selected indicators were transformed into a **scoring scale ranging from 1 to 6**. This scoring procedure allows the monitoring tool to provide a clear visual representation of relative performance across Member States, while maintaining consistency across indicators of different units and magnitudes. A value of **0 was used to indicate missing data**.

Not all indicators have the same orientation in terms of performance. For instance, a higher value of *resource productivity* indicates a positive outcome, whereas a higher value of *GHG emissions per unit of output* indicates a negative outcome. To account for this, each indicator was assigned a **directionality** (“positive” or “negative”):

- **Positive indicators (“pos”)**: higher values represent better performance (e.g., resource productivity, circular material use rate).
- **Negative indicators (“neg”)**: higher values represent worse performance (e.g., GHG emissions, material consumption per capita).

This directionality ensured that scoring remained consistent across the entire set of indicators, with **6 always reflecting the best performance and 1 the worst performance**.

The scoring system followed a **max-min class approach**:

1. **Identify range**: For each indicator, the **minimum and maximum values** across countries were identified considering all available years.
2. **Divide range into six equal intervals**: The distance between the minimum and maximum was divided into **six equally sized classes**, each corresponding to a performance score between 1 and 6.
3. **Assign scores**: Each country’s performance on a given indicator was then assigned to one of these six classes, based on its position within the range.

For **positive indicators**, countries with values closer to the maximum received higher scores (e.g., 6 = best performer). For **negative indicators**, the scoring was inverted so that lower values received higher scores (e.g., 6 = lowest GHG emissions). **As an example**, suppose that the indicator “GHG emissions intensity” ranges from 10 g/€ (best performing country) to 70 g/€ (worst performing country). The range (60 g/€) is divided into six equal classes of 10 g/€ each:

- 10-20 g/€ → Score 6 (best performance)
- 21-30 g/€ → Score 5
- 31-40 g/€ → Score 4
- 41-50 g/€ → Score 3
- 51-60 g/€ → Score 2
- 61-70 g/€ → Score 1 (worst performance)

If a country records **35 g/€**, it falls into the **31-40 g/€ interval**, and is therefore assigned a **score of 4**.

When data were not available for a country, a **score of 0** was assigned. This ensured that missing observations were clearly identifiable in the benchmarking exercise and avoided biasing cross-country comparisons.

3.1.7 Step 7: Organising the indicators into key areas

The final step of the benchmarking methodology involved **structuring the selected indicators into coherent key areas**, to ensure that the monitoring tool could both reflect policy-relevant dimensions and provide an effective user experience.

At the outset, our ambition was to align the monitoring framework with the **five Societal Objectives (SO1-SO5)** of the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System. However, following internal consultations, in particular with knowledge exchange with WP5, which focused on policy instruments, it was decided to **exclude SO1 (Food and Nutrition Security)**. This decision reflected the fact that food and nutrition issues were not directly addressed in SUSTRACK and would have complicated consistency with sectoral policy recommendations, which concentrate on textiles, plastics, chemicals, and construction. As a result, the interim version of the monitoring tool was structured around **four key areas**, broadly corresponding to SO2-SO5.

While the initial alignment captured the main bioeconomy dimensions, additional adjustments were necessary to ensure that the **visualisation in spider charts** remained both interpretable and technically feasible. Two key considerations drove these refinements:

1. **Comprehensibility:** Each spider chart should convey a **reasonable amount of information** to the user. Including too many indicators risks overloading the chart and making the results difficult to interpret.
2. **Technical feasibility:** The plotting of spider charts required that the **names of indicators remain legible**. This imposed a practical limit on the number of indicators per chart. Based on tests, we set a maximum of **around 10 indicators per spider chart**.

To respect these constraints, the indicators initially linked to SO2 (Managing Natural Resources Sustainably) and SO3 (Reducing dependence on non-renewable unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad) were **merged into a single area: “Sustainable and Renewable Resource Use.”** This ensured a balanced distribution of indicators across charts without fragmenting related themes.

The final organisation of the benchmarking framework was thus structured into **three overarching key areas**, operationalised through **four spider charts**:

- **Environmental Performance of the Bioeconomy**
 - One spider chart with **10 indicators**, covering the environmental impacts of bio-based production and consumption (e.g., emissions, material footprint and water exploitation).

- **Bioeconomy Competitiveness and Jobs**
 - Two spider charts:
 - **GVA per person employed in the bioeconomy (10 indicators)**

- **Employment in bioeconomy sectors (10 indicators)**

- **Sustainable and Renewable Resource Use**

- One spider chart with **9 indicators**, combining metrics from the original SO2 and SO3 to capture both resource management and biobased material contribution to the economy.

This final disposition strikes a balance between **policy alignment, analytical robustness, and user-friendliness**, enabling stakeholders to intuitively explore the benchmarking results while maintaining coherence with the project’s objectives.

3.2 Methodology for calculating LULUCF Distance-to-Target scores

The LULUCF sector plays a central role in the EU’s climate commitments. According to Regulation (EU) 2023/839, the LULUCF sector covers emissions and removals of greenhouse gases (GHGs) resulting from land use activities such as forestry, cropland, and grassland management. Member

States are required to ensure that accounted emissions from LULUCF are balanced by at least an equivalent amount of accounted removals during the 2021-2030 period, with specific targets defined per country. These targets reflect the capacity of national territories to act as carbon sinks and are key to achieving the EU’s overall climate neutrality objectives.

This section outlines the methodology used to compute **distance-to-target scores** for LULUCF emissions and removals across European countries. The aim is to evaluate whether Member States are on track with their country-specific LULUCF commitments, while ensuring comparability across countries with very different territorial configurations and magnitudes of emissions or removals.

3.2.1 Conceptual approach

LULUCF performance values can be **positive or negative**, where:

- **Negative values of GHG_LULUCF ($P < 0$)** indicate **net removals** (sequestration) of CO₂, which is desirable.
- **Positive values of GHG_LULUCF ($P > 0$)** indicate **net emissions** of CO₂, which is undesirable.
- **Targets (T) can also be positive (expected emissions) or negative (expected removals)**, depending on national circumstances.

The key challenge lies in the fact that “better performance” is not always associated with higher or lower numbers in absolute terms, but with **directionality relative to the target**. For example, -1000 kt CO₂e indicates stronger removals (better) than -500 kt CO₂e, while 5 kt CO₂e emissions are better than 50 kt CO₂e.

3.2.2 Determining the emission-path Direction

To consistently interpret performance, we first determine whether a country’s performance (P) is moving in the **right or wrong direction** relative to its target (T). The emission-path direction (D) is assigned according to the following rules:

Table 1: Rules to define emission-path directionality

Case	Performance (P)	Target (T)	Interpretation	D
1	P < T (more negative than target)	T < 0 (removal target)	Better than target (more removals than required)	1
2	P > T (less negative than target)	T < 0 (removal target)	Worse than target (fewer removals than required)	-1
3	P < T (lower emissions)	T > 0 (emissions target)	Better than target (lower emissions than allowed)	1

Case	Performance (P)	Target (T)	Interpretation	D
4	$P > T$ (higher emissions)	$T > 0$ (emissions target)	Worse than target (higher emissions)	-1
5	$P < 0$ (net removals)	$T > 0$ (emissions allowed)	Much better than target (already removing CO ₂ while emissions are permitted)	1
6	$P > 0$ (emitting)	$T < 0$ (removal target)	Much worse than target (emitting while removals are required)	-1

This classification ensures that **removals are always rewarded** and **excess emissions are penalised**, regardless of the sign or magnitude of the target.

3.2.3 Computing the distance and score

Step 1: Compute absolute distance to the target

$$Distance = |P - T| \times D$$

- The distance represents how far performance (P) is from the target (T).
- The sign reflects whether the performance is better (+) or worse (-) than the target.

Step 2: Normalise the distance to compute the score

$$Score = Distance / |T|$$

- The score is expressed as a **relative measure** rather than an absolute difference in kilotonnes of CO₂.
- This prevents larger countries with greater sinks or emissions from being disproportionately penalised or rewarded.

3.2.4 Interpretation of Scores

- **Score = 0** → Performance matches the target exactly ($P = T$).
- **Score > 0** → Performance is better than the target (e.g., greater removals or lower emissions than required).
- **Score < 0** → Performance is worse than the target (e.g., higher emissions or fewer removals than required).

This relative and direction-sensitive approach ensures that LULUCF performance is evaluated in a way that is fair, comparable, and policy-relevant across Member States, despite their diverse territorial conditions and commitments. Figure 4 shows the results obtained by country from 2016 to 2022.

D2.4 Bioeconomy assessment and monitoring framework and description of dashboard

Figure 4: LULUCF Distance to Target Scores by country (2016- 2022)

3.3 Bioeconomy assessment through clustering approach

The SUSTRACK monitoring system has been primarily designed as a framework to assess country performance through benchmarking across a set of key thematic areas. While its main function is to support country-level assessments, this report extends its conceptual foundation through a cluster analysis to identify common performance profiles among European countries.

It should be noted that this analysis cannot be directly performed within the SUSTRACK tool, as it is not a built-in feature. The clustering exercise is an independent analytical extension that uses the same set of indicators underpinning the SUSTRACK framework. It requires additional data processing and statistical analysis, including indicator harmonisation and the application of clustering techniques.

The analysis was based on the headline indicators representing the three key dimensions of the SUSTRACK framework:

- Sustainable and renewable resource use,
- Environmental performance, and
- Competitiveness and jobs.

A k-means clustering algorithm (Kaufman & Rousseeuw, 2008) was applied to group countries according to their performance within each dimension. The optimal number of clusters was identified using the elbow and silhouette (Rousseeuw, 1987) methods, with four clusters retained for comparability across the three dimensions. The underlying dataset was constructed from data sources as indicated in , covering primarily 2021-2022 depending on availability. Indicators were standardised to remove scale effects, except for distance-to-target measures (i.e., LULUCF indicator) already expressed in normalised form.

The resulting clusters were labelled to represent increasing levels of performance and structural maturity:

- Emerging,
- Developing,
- Mature, and
- Leading.

Cluster assignments were mapped geographically to visualise spatial patterns in bioeconomy development. Finally, cross-comparison among the three dimensions allowed for the exploration of potential synergies and trade-offs between environmental, economic, and resource management performance.

3.4 Definition of synergies and trade-off between bioeconomy indicators and SDGs

To expand the information related to the indicators to be added to the tool, a methodology was developed to link them to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In this evaluation, the first step we took was to identify whether there was a relationship and, if so, determine whether this relationship was positive or negative. The work was based on the analysis of a set of 574 indicators related to one or more of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These indicators have been collected during T2.1 and T2.3, spanning multiple sources such as the EU-BMS (particularly

for national-level indicators), FADN⁴ (for regional-level indicators at NUTS 2 and NUTS 3), FAO, as well as insights from the SUSTRACK case studies carried out in WP3. Each indicator included its corresponding unit of measurement, such as percentages, tonnes, grams per euro, or units per hectare, which helped contextualise its nature and scale and supported a more accurate interpretation. This information was particularly important when analysing potential linkages with SDGs, as the same variable can have a very different meaning depending on how it is expressed. For instance, an indicator of resource efficiency can be formulated either as euro per kilogram of material used (€/kg) or as kilograms of material used per euro of output (kg/€). While both describe the relationship between economic output and material consumption, their interpretation in relation to SDG 8 (economic growth) and SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production) changes substantially: in the first case, higher values indicate better efficiency and a positive contribution to sustainability goals, whereas in the second, higher values denote more resource-intensive production and therefore a negative relationship. Including the units of measurement was thus essential to correctly interpret the direction and magnitude of each indicator's contribution to specific SDGs and to avoid misclassification of synergies or trade-offs.

To facilitate visualisation, organisation, and further analysis, the indicators were compiled in an Excel spreadsheet (Annex 1), allowing for a systematic and orderly workflow.

A literature review was then conducted to identify the relationship between each indicator and the SDGs. When a direct relationship was found in the reviewed sources, it was marked in the spreadsheet using the following numbers:

- 3 for strong and clearly positive relationships,
- -3 for clearly negative relationships,
- 7 when the relationship was both positive and negative depending on the context.

In cases where no direct mention was found in the literature, a qualitative assessment based on expert judgment was carried out, supported by the reading of relevant documents related to both the indicator and the SDGs. These inferred relationships were noted as:

- 1 for assumed positive relationships,
- -1 for assumed negative relationships,
- 7 for ambivalent relationships.

It is worth noting that in some cases, the relationship between an indicator and an SDG may vary depending on the **value of the ratio** (e.g., whether it is high or low), or on the **perspective from which it is analysed**. In other words, if a certain condition or outcome occurs, the relationship may be positive; however, if the opposite occurs, the relationship may be negative.

⁴ Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). Note that as of 2025, the Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN) is set to replace the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). The FSDN will build on the FADN's legacy, expanding its scope to cover not only farms' income and business activities but also information on their environmental and social sustainability performance.

For example, the indicator “Crop protection” (€) plays a crucial role in food security and agricultural sustainability, interacting in various ways with the SDGs. With the help of the report *A Guide to SDG Interactions* by the International Science Council, we identified the following interactions:

Positive interactions:

- **SDG 2: Zero Hunger** - Effective crop protection helps reduce agricultural losses, ensuring sufficient and high-quality food production.
- **SDG 1: No Poverty & SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth** - Implementing sustainable practices in crop protection can increase the income of small and medium-sized producers, improving their livelihoods.

Negative interactions:

- **SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being** - Excessive or inappropriate use of pesticides can harm human and animal health.
- **SDG 15: Life on Land** - Intensive pesticide application can damage biodiversity and ecosystems.

In summary, crop protection can contribute positively to the SDGs if it is based on sustainable and responsible practices. However, an unsustainable approach can lead to negative impacts on health and the environment.

Academic databases on Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, Scopus, Springer, and ResearchGate have been used, along with reports from organisations such as the FAO, the International Council for Science, among others. All bibliographic references used are documented in the Annex 1, in a dedicated column at the end of each row corresponding to each indicator. This ensures the traceability of sources and the transparency of the analysis process.

4 SUSTRACK MONITORING SYSTEM

4.1 Objectives

The SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment Tool has been designed to support policymakers, researchers, and practitioners in navigating the complexity of the CBE transition. Within the SUSTRACK project, specifically in WP2, T2.3, clear objectives were defined to guide the development of the monitoring system. These objectives are threefold:

- Support understanding of good management for the transition to a CBE (through spider charts and benchmarking).
- Elicit the connections between indicators and SDGs (through heatmaps).
- Facilitate access to available resources, including existing indicators, data, and methods (through comprehensive bioeconomy indicator repository).

Figure 5 presents these objectives and shows how each of them has been operationalised into practical features of the digital tool. In the figure, the objectives are paired with snapshots of the

relevant sections of the platform, illustrating how they have been concretely addressed and fulfilled.

Figure 5: SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment Tool's objectives and respective operationalisation in the tool

A specific objective of T2.3 was to elicit connections with, or provide information on, thresholds, which can be interpreted in different ways. Thresholds may refer to performance thresholds (relative comparisons across countries), sustainability thresholds (biophysical or ecological limits), or normative thresholds (societal or policy-defined goals). **In this report, and in the SUSTRACK monitoring tool, thresholds have been operationalised in a simplified way as performance thresholds, exemplified by a ranking approach that identifies best and worst performers for each selected indicator.** While this provides a practical entry point for benchmarking and hotspot analysis, it represents a reductionist interpretation when compared to the broader meaning of sustainability thresholds.

A more comprehensive and normative interpretation of thresholds, including their sustainability dimension, is provided in D2.5: Analysis and development of sustainability thresholds. This complementary work delves into thresholds not only as relative benchmarks, but as fundamental reference points for evaluating whether bioeconomy developments stay within safe operating spaces from environmental, social, and policy perspectives.

The following sections of this chapter provide a detailed description of the structure, content, and functionalities of the SUSTRACK Monitoring System, clarifying how the tool translates these objectives into practice.

4.2 Key areas and headline indicators

The SUSTRACK monitoring system includes **21 indicators**, organised into **three key areas of interest**. These areas reflect the objectives and guiding principles of the monitoring framework introduced above:

1. **Sustainable and renewable resource use** - linked to SO2 and SO4 and the principle “Use resources efficiently”. Indicators in this area measure resource productivity, waste

generation and management, and the contribution of bio-based materials to the economy and energy system.

2. **Environmental performance of the bio-based economy** - linked to **SO3** and the principle “*Reduce GHG emissions*”. This area informs on sectoral emission intensities (GHG emissions/GVA), the biomass footprint, and water exploitation.
3. **Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs** - linked to **SO5** and the principle of “*Decoupling*”, providing insights into the economic growth dimension of the bioeconomy. Indicators include apparent labour productivity in bio-based sectors and the contribution of bio-based activities to the overall employment.

Each key area, along with its underlying indicators, is described in more detail below. For information on the selection process and data processing methods, the reader is referred to Section 4 (Methods).

4.2.1 Sustainable and Renewable Resource Use

Figure 6 shows the spider chart embedded in the Sustrack dashboard, serving as the visual representation of the benchmark analysis for the key area of *sustainable and renewable resource use*.

Figure 6: Indicators included in “Sustainable and renewable resource use” spider-chart

The area provides a clear overview of how efficiently resources are utilized across countries, informing on circularity waste management and generation and productivity. Specifically, this area includes the following headline indicators:

- 1 **Energy productivity (EUR/kg of oil equivalent):** Calculated as the ratio of gross domestic product (GDP) to gross available energy for a given year. It measures the productivity of

energy consumption and provides insights into the degree of decoupling between energy use and economic growth.

This indicator is also used in UN SDG 7.3.1, “Energy intensity measured in terms of primary energy and GDP” (UNITED NATIONS, 2024) and included in the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS). Source: Eurostat (nrg_ind_ep).

- 2 **Recycling rate of municipal waste (percentage):** Measures the share of recycled municipal waste in total municipal waste generation. It is directly linked to **SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production)** and **SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure)**.

The indicator is included in both the **EU-BMS** and the **EU Circular Economy Monitoring Framework**. Source: Eurostat (env_wasmun).

- 3 **Circular material use rate (percentage):** Measures the share of material recovered and reintroduced into the economy, thereby reducing the extraction of primary raw materials, in overall material use. It is defined as the ratio of circular use of materials to overall material use, where:

3.1.1 *Overall material use = Domestic Material Consumption (DMC) + circular use of materials*

3.1.2 *Circular use of materials = (waste recycled domestically - imported waste for recovery + exported waste for recovery)*

A higher value indicates greater use of secondary materials as substitution of primary raw materials, reducing the environmental impacts of extraction. The indicator is closely tied to several **European Green Deal objectives** (clean energy, circular industry, resource-efficient construction) and to **SDGs 12 and 9** (Responsible Consumption and Production and Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure). It is a **key indicator** in the **EU-BMS** and **EU Circular Economy Monitoring Framework** and used to monitor **SDG 12.4.1** “Number of parties to international multilateral environmental agreements on hazardous waste, and other chemicals that meet their commitments and obligations in transmitting information as required by each relevant agreement”. Source: Eurostat (env_ac_cur).

- 4 **Total food waste (Tonnes per capita):** This indicator measures the amount of food waste generated per year in EU Member States across the different stages of the food supply chain. The underlying model was developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) (De Laurentiis et al., 2024). Food waste is a critical challenge for sustainability, given its implications for resource efficiency, greenhouse gas emissions, and food system resilience. The indicator directly links to European Green Deal objectives, in particular: 2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy; and 2.1.6. From ‘Farm to Fork’: designing a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. It is also closely tied to SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). While the indicator is included in the EU-BMS, for comparability across countries we expressed it in per capita terms (i.e., dividing total food waste by the national population).

In the benchmarking analysis, due to space constraints, we prioritised **total** food waste generation. However, in the cross-country assessment module, food waste data are also available by stage of the food supply chain (e.g., primary production, processing and manufacturing, retail and distribution, food services consumption and households’ consumption). Source data: JRC (Sala & De Laurentiis, 2023).

5 **Domestic material consumption (biomass share, %):** This indicator quantifies the share of **biomass** in the total **domestic material consumption (DMC)** of an economy. DMC represents the total amount of materials directly used by an economy and is calculated as the sum of four material categories: biomass, metal ores, non-metallic minerals, and fossil energy materials and carriers. By focusing on the **biomass share of DMC**, this indicator provides insight into the relative importance of bio-based resources within the overall material mix of national economies. Monitoring the role of biomass is crucial for assessing progress towards a more **sustainable, bio-based, and resource-efficient economy**. The indicator is part of **Eurostat’s Economy-Wide Material Flow Accounts (EW-MFA)**, which offer a comprehensive overview of material flows into and out of economies. It contributes to several **European Green Deal objectives**, including: **2.1.2. Supplying clean, affordable and secure energy; 2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy; 2.1.4. Building and renovating in an energy and resource-efficient way; 2.1.5. Accelerating the shift to sustainable and smart mobility; 2.1.6. From ‘Farm to Fork’: designing a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system**. It is also directly linked to **SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production)**, and is used to monitor **SDG 12.2.2 “Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP”/ 8.4.2 “Domestic material consumption (DMC) and DMC per capita, per GDP”**, on resource use efficiency (UNITED NATIONS, 2024). The indicator is included in the **EU-BMS**. Source EUROSTAT (env_ac_mfa).

6 **Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption (percentage, %):** This indicator measures the share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption, in line with the **Renewable Energy Directive**. Gross final energy consumption includes the energy used by end-consumers (final energy consumption), grid losses, and the self-consumption of power plants. It provides a central measure of the **energy transition**, highlighting the role of renewable sources in replacing fossil fuels.

The indicator is directly linked to **European Green Deal objectives: 2.1.2. Supplying clean, affordable and secure energy**. It also contributes to several **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**, in particular: **SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy); SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production); SDG 13 (Climate Action)**. Specifically, it is used to monitor **UN SDG 7.2.1 (Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption) (UNITED NATIONS, 2024)**. The indicator is included in the **EU-BMS**. Source: EUROSTAT (nrg_ind_ren).

7 **Total recovered biowaste (kilotonnes dry/person):** This indicator measures the amount of **biowaste recovered** from households, industry, and agriculture. Data are drawn from Eurostat’s waste treatment statistics [env_wastrt], which disaggregate biowaste by treatment option and by stream (e.g., household paper and cardboard, untreated waste, food waste). While the underlying dataset allows detailed analysis by waste stream and source, in the **benchmarking analysis** we prioritised **total recovered biowaste**. To enable **cross-country comparability**, values were expressed on a **per capita basis** by dividing by population.

The indicator is included in the **EU-BMS** and relates to **European Green Deal objectives**, especially: **2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy**. It also supports **SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production)**. Source: JRC_BIOMASS(Joint Research Centre, 2023).

8 **Total generated biowaste (kilotonnes dry/person):** This indicator captures the amount of **biowaste generated** annually by households and industry. Data are reported by EU Member States under the **Waste Statistics Regulation** and published by Eurostat. Biowaste categories cover a broad set of material streams, such as **household food waste, paper and cardboard,**

garden and park waste, and selected industrial organic waste streams. As with recovered biowaste, this indicator was transformed into **per capita terms** to ensure comparability across countries. In the benchmarking analysis, the **total generated biowaste** was prioritised over a breakdown by source or stream due to space constraints.

The indicator is included in the **EU-BMS** and contributes to **European Green Deal objectives**, notably: **2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy**. It is also linked to **SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production)**. Source: JRC_BIOMASS (Joint Research Centre, 2023).

- 9 **Resource productivity (EUR/kg):** Resource productivity is defined as the ratio between **gross domestic product (GDP)** and **domestic material consumption (DMC)**. DMC represents the total amount of materials directly used by an economy and is calculated as:

$$DMC = Domestic\ extraction + Imports - Exports$$

It is important to note that DMC reflects **apparent consumption**, not final consumption, and excludes upstream resource flows associated with imports and exports.

Improvements in resource productivity reflect the **efficiency of material use**, supporting the **decoupling** of economic growth from resource consumption. Decoupling is central to the **transition towards a circular economy**, as it aims to reduce environmental pressures while maintaining economic development. Resource productivity is included in the **EU Circular Economy Monitoring Framework**. Source EUROSTAT (env_ac_rp).

4.2.2 Environmental performance of the bio-based economy

Figure 7 shows the **spider chart embedded in the Sustrack dashboard**, serving as the visual representation of the benchmark analysis for the key area of *Environmental performance of the bio-based economy*.

Figure 7: Indicators included in “Environmental performance of the bio-based economy” spider-chart

This area assesses how efficiently from an environmental perspective, resources are used and informs on emissions intensities, water exploitation and resource footprint. Namely, it includes the following headline indicators:

- 1 **GHG emissions intensities by NACE (grams per euro):** This indicator measures the **amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions per unit of economic output**, providing insights into the **environmental efficiency of production activities**. By expressing emissions in relation to economic activity, it allows for meaningful comparisons across countries and sectors, and over time, as it accounts for differences in economic scale.

Data are presented by **economic activities classified under NACE Rev. 2**, with a focus on sectors relevant to the bio-based economy. These include:

- Agriculture
- Forestry and logging
- Fishing and aquaculture
- Food, beverages and tobacco industries
- Textile sector
- Wood products and furniture
- Paper and paper products

The indicator is computed as the ratio between **GHG emissions (in CO₂-equivalents)** and **gross value added (GVA, in euros)**, though other economic parameters such as production output and employment may also be used. GVA is particularly suitable as it reflects the contribution of each activity to the economy, making it possible to evaluate whether sectors are **decoupling economic growth from emissions**. A **decrease in emissions intensity** means that a sector is producing the same or greater economic value with fewer emissions, indicating improvements in environmental performance and efficiency. Conversely, stable or increasing intensity values highlight areas where further **policy action** may be needed. It should be noted that **household emissions** are excluded from this indicator, as households do not generate gross value added.

This indicator is aligned with the EU's **climate neutrality objective by 2050**, ensuring that competitiveness, prosperity, and fairness are achieved through the **decoupling of economic activities from GHG emissions**. It is also linked to the monitoring of **SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure)**, specifically **SDG indicator 9.4.1 "Air emission intensity from industry"** (UNITED NATIONS, 2024). *Source: Eurostat (env_ac_ainah_r2).*

- 2 **Net GHG emissions (emissions and removals) from LULUCF (Mtonnes CO₂e):** This indicator captures **emissions and removals of greenhouse gases (mainly CO₂)** from the **Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF)** sector. It covers "managed lands" - including forest land, cropland, grassland, wetlands, settlements, and other lands - and accounts for the following carbon pools:

- Living biomass (above- and below-ground vegetation)
- Dead organic matter (deadwood and litter)
- Soil organic carbon (mineral and organic soils)
- Harvested wood products (e.g., timber used in construction or furniture)

This indicator is crucial for assessing the role of land management in climate mitigation. Net removals indicate that LULUCF acts as a carbon sink, while net emissions show a contribution to climate change.

To make this indicator suitable for **benchmarking analysis**, we transformed it into a **distance-to-target score** (see methodology in Chapter 4.3).

Related **Green Deal Objectives**: 2.1.1. Increasing the EU’s climate ambition for 2030 and 2050; 2.1.2. Supplying clean, affordable and secure energy; 2.1.4. Building and renovating in an energy and resource efficient way. Related **Sustainable Development Goals**: Goal 13: Climate Action. EUROSTAT (env_air_gge); EEA (European Environment Agency, 2025).

3 **Water exploitation index (percentage, %)**: The **water exploitation index (WEI+)** measures **total water consumption** as a share of **renewable freshwater resources** available in a given territory and period. It accounts for the balance between **water abstractions** and **water returns** to the environment by economic sectors, with the difference considered as **net consumption**. WEI+ serves as an indicator of **water stress**:

- Values above **20%** are generally seen as a warning threshold for water scarcity.
- Values above **40%** indicate **severe water scarcity**, pointing to unsustainable water use.

While WEI+ provides a useful aggregate measure, annual national-level calculations can mask **seasonal or regional water stress**, since water availability and demand are unevenly distributed across time and space. Related **Green Deal Objectives**: 2.1.1. Increasing the EU’s climate ambition for 2030 and 2050. 2.1.7. Preserving and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity. Related **Sustainable Development Goals**: Goal 6: Clean Water and Sanitation; Goal 13: Climate Action. Source Eurostat (sdg_06_60).

4 **Material footprint (biomass) intensity (kilogram per dollar of GDP in USD)**: This indicator measures the **total amount of biomass in raw materials terms extracted globally to meet final consumption demands**, expressed relative to gross domestic product (GDP). While *Domestic Material Consumption (biomass share)* measures the proportion of biomass in the materials directly used within an economy, and the Circular Material Rate quantifies the share of secondary materials reintroduced into the economy, the Material footprint (biomass) intensity takes a **consumption-based perspective**. It accounts for all raw materials extracted globally to satisfy a country’s final demand, including those embodied in imports. This makes it particularly suited to assessing the **global resource implications of national consumption patterns**, complementing the production-based measures.

It provides insight into the **resource efficiency of economic growth** by linking material use to economic output, and serves as a proxy for the **environmental pressures** associated with consumption. A lower intensity value suggests that fewer materials are required to generate each unit of economic value, indicating progress towards **decoupling economic growth from resource use**. Conversely, high values signal resource-inefficient consumption patterns, with stronger environmental impacts through extraction, processing, and waste generation. Material footprint intensity is a critical measure for **assessing the sustainability of the bioeconomy**.

It provides evidence on whether growth in the bioeconomy is achieved through more efficient use of biomass or through increased extraction and consumption. It is directly relevant to policies on **resource efficiency, circularity, and the transition to climate neutrality**, and supports monitoring progress towards the **EU Circular Economy Action Plan and Bioeconomy Strategy**. Related **Green Deal Objectives**: 2.1.2. Supplying clean, affordable and secure energy; 2.1.4. Building and renovating in an energy and resource efficient way; 2.1.5. Accelerating the shift to sustainable and smart mobility; 2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean

and circular economy; 2.1.6. From ‘Farm to Fork’: designing a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. **Related Sustainable Development Goals:** Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production and used to monitor: UN SDG 12.2.1 “Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP”/ 8.4.1 “Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP” (UNITED NATIONS, 2024). Source data: UNEP (UN Environment Programme, 2025).

4.2.3 Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs

Figure 8 shows the **spider charts embedded in the Sustrack dashboard**, serving as the visual representation of the benchmark analysis for the key area of *Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs*. The spider chart on the left informs on the Gross value added (GVA) per person employed across bioeconomy sectors, while the spider chart on the right shows the share of employment by bio-based sector over total bioeconomy employment.

Figure 8: Indicators included in “Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs” area

This area assesses how **competitive the bio-based sectors are** and **which sectors contribute the most to employment in the bioeconomy**. Competitiveness is primarily measured through productivity and value creation, while employment highlights the role of bio-based sectors in providing jobs and supporting regional economies. Both aspects are highly policy-relevant: improving productivity ensures long-term competitiveness and resilience of the EU bioeconomy, while understanding employment contributions helps identify opportunities for **just transition, rural development, and social inclusion**. These indicators are also central for monitoring progress under the **EU Bioeconomy Strategy, the European Green Deal, and the SDGs**, as they inform decisions on innovation, skills, and sustainable growth.

The following headline indicators are included:

- 1 **Gross value added per person employed in bioeconomy (1000 EUR per person):** This indicator measures the **apparent labour productivity** of bio-based sectors by dividing gross value added at factor costs by the number of persons employed in each sector. It reflects how efficiently labour is used to generate economic value. Bio-based sectors considered include:

- Agriculture

- Forestry and logging
- Fishing and aquaculture
- Food, beverages, and tobacco industries
- Textiles
- Wood products (except furniture)
- Paper and paper products
- Manufacture of furniture
- Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and preparations
- Manufacture of rubber and plastics products

This indicator provides insights into the **competitiveness and innovation capacity** of the bioeconomy. Sectors with higher labour productivity tend to be more competitive, technologically advanced, and better positioned to contribute to economic growth while maintaining environmental sustainability. **Labour productivity** is a key target for EU competitiveness and growth strategies. In the bioeconomy, increasing productivity is closely linked to investments in research, innovation, skills, and sustainable practices. It also ensures that the bioeconomy contributes to resilient value chains and supports the transition towards climate neutrality. **Related Green Deal Objectives:** 2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy; 2.1.6. From ‘Farm to Fork’: designing a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. **Related Sustainable Development Goals:** Goal 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth; Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure

The indicator is included in the EU-BMS and EU Bioeconomy Strategy (Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy, 2025). Source: DataM (JRC & nova-Institute, 2025).

- 2 **Share of employment by bio-based sector (% of total bio-based employment):** This indicator measures the **relative contribution of each bio-based sector to total employment in the bioeconomy**. It is calculated as the number of persons employed in a given bio-based NACE sector divided by the total number of persons employed across all bio-based sectors. This approach allows for **consistent cross-country comparison**, as it accounts for differences in the size of national labour markets. Instead of focusing only on absolute numbers of employees, it highlights the **structure of bioeconomy employment** and identifies which sectors dominate or lag in different Member States.

Sectors included are the same as in *Gross value added per person employed in bioeconomy* indicator (agriculture, forestry, fishing and aquaculture, food and beverages, textiles, wood, paper, furniture, pharmaceuticals, rubber and plastics). Employment distribution across bio-based sectors is a key dimension of the **EU Bioeconomy Strategy**, supporting policies on **skills, job creation, and regional development**. It also helps monitor the role of traditional bio-based sectors (e.g., agriculture, forestry) compared with emerging, higher-value-added sectors (e.g., biochemicals, pharmaceuticals, bio-based plastics). This is crucial to ensure the bioeconomy is not only competitive but also socially inclusive, creating jobs across regions and supporting the EU’s just transition goals. **Related Green Deal Objectives:** 2.1.3. Mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy; 2.1.6. From ‘Farm to Fork’: designing a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. **Related Sustainable Development Goals:** Goal 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth; Goal 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure. Source: **DataM (JRC & nova-Institute, 2025)**.

4.3 Assessment of Bioeconomy Performance Across European Countries

Building upon the SUSTRACK Monitoring Framework, a cluster analysis was conducted to provide an integrated overview of bioeconomy performance across European countries. Although the SUSTRACK tool itself does not include this functionality, the analysis relies on the same set of indicators used in the framework, extending its application through additional data processing and statistical methods.

By grouping countries according to their performance across the three thematic areas, environmental performance, resource management, and competitiveness and jobs, the analysis identifies common profiles and structural patterns that are not visible through individual indicators. This approach supports a more systemic understanding of how different bioeconomy models evolve across Europe and where potential synergies or trade-offs may occur. This perspective is particularly useful for policy analysis, as it identifies not only front-runners and laggards, but also intermediate groups of countries facing shared challenges and opportunities. Policy implications derived from this evidence are discussed in D5.5.

The results are presented in the following sections, where each cluster typology is described in detail together with the corresponding geographical patterns and policy interpretations. Finally, results from the three clustering analyses have been integrated into a single table to explore potential synergies and trade-offs between environmental impacts, economic competitiveness, and resource management, revealing whether a country performs better in one area than another.

4.3.1 Resource management cluster results

Figure 9 shows the country classification according to resource management, while Table 2 provides the indicators' average across clusters. To note that although the key area on resource management originally included nine headline indicators, three of them, *share of renewable energy*, *resource productivity*, and *energy productivity*, were excluded from the clustering analysis. The main reason for this choice was to maintain conceptual coherence within the cluster and avoid mixing indicators that describe broader economic or energy system dynamics with those reflecting more direct resource management outcomes. In practice, indicators such as renewable energy share and energy productivity also capture upstream energy transition processes rather than end-of-pipe or circular resource management performance, and their inclusion would have complicated the interpretation of clusters. The final selection therefore prioritised end-of-pipe and circularity-related indicators, providing a more focused and consistent basis for assessing resource management performance across countries.

Emerging bioeconomies, i.e., Romania and Bulgaria, show the lowest performance across all indicators. The **circular material use rate (8.6%)** and **municipal waste recycling (16%)** are far below the EU average. Moreover, the gap between **biowaste generated (0.30 tonnes per capita)** and **biowaste recovered (0.17 tonnes per capita)** highlights inefficiencies in waste management systems. The **biomass share of domestic material consumption (11.4%)** is also relatively low, suggesting limited reliance on renewable material flows. These countries are only at the beginning of their circular bio-based transition and would benefit most from targeted support to strengthen basic collection and recycling systems, enforce landfill diversion, and promote extended producer responsibility schemes.

Developing bioeconomies show mixed performance as they include countries from southern, eastern and northern Europe. In general, the **circular material use rate is still low (6.1%)**, but their **recycling rate of municipal waste (38%)** is considerably higher than in the Emerging group. The **biomass share of DMC (26.2%)** indicates a stronger connection to bio-based activities, and the gap between biowaste generated and biomass recovered is also very small (0,26 vs 0,20), indicating effective waste collection systems. However, **food waste generation (210 kg per capita)** is among the highest, pointing to inefficiencies along the supply chain. These countries would benefit from **scaling up biowaste valorisation technologies** and reducing food waste.

Figure 9: Clusters results resource management (2022)

Mature bioeconomies, which include Italy, France, Sweden and Finland among others, combine relatively strong performance with stable waste management systems. The **circular material use rate (13.2%)** is above the EU average, while **municipal waste recycling (51%)** and **biowaste recovery (0.32 vs 0.34 tonnes generated)** highlight effective infrastructures for material recovery. These countries also show the **lowest food waste generation (147 kg per capita)**, suggesting progress in food chain efficiency. The **biomass share of DMC (21.4%)** is moderate, reflecting balanced reliance on renewable resources. These countries have largely consolidated basic systems and now face more systemic challenges: scaling bio-based innovation, preventing waste generation at source, and integrating circularity across industrial sectors.

Leading bioeconomies, including Belgium and the Netherlands, are the top performers in resource management. With a **circular material use rate of 22.8%** and **municipal waste recycling at 56%**, these countries set benchmarks for Europe. Biowaste recovery is nearly complete (**0.62 vs 0.63 tonnes generated**), while the **biomass share of DMC (34.3%)** is the highest, signalling strong integration of renewable resources into their economies. However, **food waste generation (253 kg per capita)** is also the highest, pointing to persistent inefficiencies in consumption and distribution despite advanced recovery systems. These countries demonstrate the frontier of resource management but face the challenge of **reducing food waste generation** while maintaining high recovery and circularity levels. They provide useful lessons for scaling high-value valorisation chains.

Table 2: Resource management indicators average by clusters typology

Cluster	Circular material rate (percentage)	Recycling rate of municipal waste	Total generated biowaste (tonnes dry per capita)	Total recovered biowaste (tonnes dry per capita)	Domestic Material Consumption (biomass share)	Total food waste generation along supply chain (Kg per capita)
Emerging	8,63	16,05	0,30	0,17	11,43	139,19
Developing	6,13	38,13	0,26	0,20	26,23	210,31
Mature	13,23	50,88	0,34	0,32	21,37	147,64
Leading	22,75	56,15	0,63	0,62	34,29	253,14

4.3.2 Environmental cluster results

The clustering of countries based on environmental performance shows a clear divide between Western and Central Europe on the one hand, and Eastern Europe on the other (Figure 10). Countries in the leading cluster, largely from **Western and Central Europe and including Finland and Slovakia**, present the most favourable profile: their **bioeconomy emission intensity is the lowest ($\approx 481 \text{ gCO}_2\text{e}$)** across all groups, their biomass footprint is relatively limited (**0.13**), and they are already slightly above their 2030 LULUCF targets. This suggests that their bioeconomy systems are comparatively efficient and low-carbon, while land-use and forestry sectors are contributing positively to climate targets. In these cases, the policy challenge is less about catching up and more about consolidating existing achievements, ensuring that improvements are sustained, and avoiding the displacement of environmental pressures to external suppliers of biomass.

By contrast, most **Eastern European countries fall into the developing cluster**. Here, emission intensity is considerably higher ($\approx 791 \text{ gCO}_2\text{e}$), the biomass footprint remains elevated (027), and the LULUCF score hovers just below zero, meaning that countries are not yet securely on track to meet their 2030 LULUCF targets. This combination indicates that, while land-based mitigation potential is not entirely out of reach, there is a pressing need to decarbonise bio-based sectors and strengthen land-management practices to close the gap towards climate commitments.

Latvia, classified in the emerging group, represents a particular case. Despite its strong forestry sector, it **combines very high emission intensity with one of the lowest LULUCF scores**, far

below the 2030 benchmark. This reflects both the **challenges of managing extensive carbon-rich ecosystems such as forests and peatlands, and the difficulty of balancing intensive biomass use with climate objectives.** For Latvia and similar cases, immediate efforts are required to restore and enhance natural sinks while also reducing reliance on emission-intensive bioeconomic activities.

Czechia stands alone in the mature cluster, but this classification should be read with caution. Its indicators place it between the developing and leading groups, yet its negative LULUCF score signals that it is **not currently on track with its climate obligations.** This highlights that “maturity” in this case should not be interpreted as strong sustainability performance; instead, Czechia reflects a more transitional position, where certain gains in emission intensity are offset by persistent land-use challenges.

Taken together, these patterns reinforce the existence of a **structural East-West divide in environmental performance** within the European bioeconomy. Western and Central European countries tend to align or even surpass their climate targets, while many Eastern and Southern regions face a double challenge of high emission intensity and insufficient land-use performance.

Figure 10: Clusters results environmental performance (2022)

Table 3: Environmental indicators average by clusters typology

Cluster	Bioeconomy emission intensity	LULUCF score	Biomass consumption footprint
Emerging	767,78	-8,68	0,27
Developing	791,40	-0,03	0,27
Mature	566,91	-3,75	0,20
Leading	480,99	0,08	0,13

4.3.3 Economic competitiveness cluster results

The clustering of economic competitiveness highlights a very different geography compared to the environmental dimension (Figure 11). Here, the divide is less about East and West and more about the level of economic development and productivity within the bioeconomy. The **leading group**, which includes **Northern Europe together with Belgium and the Netherlands**, stands out for its exceptionally high bioeconomy productivity. Although the relative **contribution of the bioeconomy to GVA and employment is modest**, around 6% in both cases, **the sector generates the highest value added per worker**. This reflects a specialised, innovation-driven bioeconomy where fewer people are employed, but those employed contribute to a highly productive and competitive sector.

The **mature cluster**, comprising much of **Central Europe along with Italy, Spain and Slovakia**, also shows a balanced performance. The bioeconomy contributes around 5% of GVA and 6% of employment, with productivity levels that are about half of the leading group. These countries combine relatively strong traditions in agriculture, forestry, and food industries with ongoing transitions towards higher-value bio-based activities. Their policy priority is to strengthen innovation and investment in biotechnologies and advanced materials, thereby bridging the gap with the high-performing Northern countries while safeguarding employment in traditional bio-based sectors.

A different picture emerges for the **developing cluster**, which includes many **Eastern European and Balkan countries as well as Portugal**. In this group, **the bioeconomy plays a visibly larger role in the economy**, contributing 8% of GVA and 12% of total employment, **but productivity remains very low**. This indicates a **labour-intensive structure**, often rooted in primary production and early-stage processing activities, with limited capacity to capture higher value along the bioeconomy value chains. The main policy challenge here is to move up the productivity ladder: supporting skills, technological upgrading, and diversification of bio-based industries while avoiding job losses in regions where employment in the sector remains a social and economic buffer.

At the lower end, the **emerging cluster is represented by countries such as Bulgaria and Romania**. Here, the bioeconomy employs nearly a quarter of the workforce (23%) and contributes 8% to GVA, but productivity is strikingly low, just under €8,000 per worker. This reflects a **structural reliance on agriculture and low-value processing**, with little integration into more advanced or knowledge-intensive bioeconomy sectors. The main challenge for these countries is how to modernise and diversify their bioeconomy without undermining its role as a major source of rural employment.

Figure 11: Cluster analysis results bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs

Table 4: Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs indicators average by clusters typology

Cluster	Bioeconomy contribution to GVA	Bioeconomy contribution to employment	Bioeconomy productivity
Leading	0,06	0,06	98,24
Mature	0,05	0,06	47,53
Developing	0,08	0,12	24,83
Emerging	0,08	0,23	7,86

4.3.4 Combined cluster analysis results

When comparing the three cluster dimensions together (Table 5), clear patterns of alignment and divergence emerge. At the top end, countries like **Belgium**, the **Netherlands**, and **Finland** consistently fall into the **leading category** across resource management, environmental performance, and competitiveness. These are the **front-runners** of the European bioeconomy,

combining circular practices, environmental progress, and strong productivity. They represent “win-win” situations where environment, markets, and innovation systems align.

A second distinct group is formed by **Austria, Germany, Italy, France, and Slovakia**, which share the exact same profile: **mature in resource management, leading in environmental performance, and mature in competitiveness**. These countries are environmentally advanced, already meeting or surpassing their LULUCF targets and lowering emission intensities, but their resource management and productivity indicators remain in the “mature” rather than “leading” category. This suggests that their bioeconomies are already sizeable and structurally robust, but the challenge is to push them further towards **value creation, innovation-driven productivity, and higher resource efficiency**. In policy terms, these countries need strategies that go beyond scaling and instead focus on upgrading quality and competitiveness within the bioeconomy.

The picture changes substantially when looking at **Eastern and Balkan countries**, where trade-offs are more evident. **Bulgaria and Romania**, for example, are classified as “emerging” in both resource management and competitiveness, while only “developing” environmentally. These profiles show **bioeconomies with large employment shares but very low productivity, combined with weak recycling and circularity rates**. Without substantial policy intervention, these countries risk being locked into low-value, resource-intensive trajectories. **Croatia, Hungary, and Poland** also cluster consistently in the “developing” category across all three areas, highlighting structural weaknesses that are difficult to address without targeted EU support.

There are also a number of **hybrid or exceptional cases** worth noting. **Latvia** is “emerging” environmentally but “developing” in resource management and competitiveness, reflecting the **specific challenges of managing forest-related emissions in a context of modest productivity**. **Cyprus** shows an unusual pattern, with “emerging” scores in resource management, “developing” environmentally, but “mature” in competitiveness, indicating that bioeconomy employment and GVA are relatively well balanced despite weak circularity. **Malta** is another case where competitiveness and environmental performance are stronger than resource management, suggesting that small states can leverage scale and specialisation differently from larger countries. Meanwhile, **Portugal and Spain** combine strong environmental performance with only moderate economic competitiveness, pointing to an imbalance between ecological progress and value creation.

Overall, the cross-comparison illustrates that **leadership across all dimensions is challenging**, with Belgium and the Netherlands being the strongest examples. More common are asymmetries, where environmental progress is not yet matched by competitiveness gains (e.g. Spain, Italy), or where strong economic performance coincides with weaker resource management (e.g. Cyprus, Malta). These divergences are not necessarily weaknesses: they can signal where targeted policy efforts could deliver convergence and create **win-win pathways**. For the leaders, the priority is consolidation and innovation; for the mature group, the focus is on boosting productivity and circularity; and for the developing/emerging countries, structural transformation and capacity-building remain the key challenges.

While the clustering exercise provides a valuable comparative overview of bioeconomy performance across Europe, it should be interpreted with caution. The results are derived from a limited set of quantitative indicators, which, although carefully selected to capture key dimensions of the bioeconomy, cannot fully reflect national specificities, policy contexts, or structural differences among countries. The clusters are therefore best understood as analytical constructs that help identify patterns and relative positions, rather than definitive classifications. For meaningful policy interpretation, these findings should be complemented with country-level

expertise and qualitative insights to validate the underlying drivers and contextual factors shaping each national bioeconomy.

Table 5: Combined results of clustering analysis

Country	Cluster Resource Management	Cluster Environment	Cluster Competitiveness and jobs
Austria	Mature	Leading	Mature
Belgium	Leading	Leading	Leading
Bulgaria	Emerging	Developing	Emerging
Cyprus	Emerging	Developing	Mature
Czechia	Na	Mature	Mature
Germany	Mature	Leading	Mature
Denmark	Developing	Leading	Leading
Estonia	Mature	Developing	Developing
Greece	Developing	Developing	na
Spain	Developing	Leading	Mature
Finland	Mature	Leading	Leading
France	Mature	Leading	Mature
Greece	Na	na	Developing
Croatia	Developing	Developing	Developing
Hungary	Developing	Developing	Developing
Ireland	Na	na	Leading
Italy	Mature	Leading	Mature
Lithuania	Na	na	Developing
Luxembourg	Na	na	Mature
Latvia	Developing	Emerging	Developing
Malta	Emerging	Leading	Mature
Netherlands	Leading	Leading	Leading
Poland	Developing	Developing	Developing
Portugal	Developing	Leading	Developing
Romania	Emerging	Developing	Emerging
Sweden	Na	na	Leading
Slovenia	Mature	Leading	Developing
Slovakia	Mature	Leading	Mature
EU27 (2020)	Mature	na	na
Luxembourg	Mature	na	na
Sweden	Mature	na	na
Lithuania	Developing	na	na

4.4 Bioeconomy and SDGs

The analysis shows that bioeconomy indicators are linked to most of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), although not all are covered with the same intensity. Several goals concentrate a higher number of associated indicators, particularly SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action). This reflects the strong connection of the bioeconomy with the sustainable management of natural resources, the energy transition, and the creation of green employment opportunities. Conversely, SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions) show a lower level of association, suggesting that the contribution of the bioeconomy in these areas is more indirect or less frequently captured by the existing indicators.

It is important to highlight that indicators are not instruments that generate impacts by themselves; rather, they serve as tools for monitoring and evaluating progress. The same indicator can show positive or negative values depending on the context, threshold, or the specific way it is articulated, but it always measures the same underlying factor. Consequently, the value of this analysis lies not in attributing impacts to the indicators, but in understanding how they are generally connected to the SDGs and identifying which dimensions of sustainability, environmental, social, or institutional, are more or less represented within the bioeconomy framework.

Some goals, such as SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land), display mixed or ambivalent associations. This variability illustrates the importance of considering the socio-environmental and sectoral context in which each indicator is applied, since the meaning of its measured values may vary depending on local priorities or resource management strategies. Such nuances reinforce the need to interpret indicator results within their specific implementation context.

Overall, the bioeconomy emerges as a key driver for advancing several SDGs, particularly those related to environmental sustainability, renewable energy, and circular production systems. However, to maximize its contribution to sustainable development, it would be necessary to complement the current indicator set with others that better reflect social and institutional dimensions, thus promoting a more comprehensive representation of the 2030 Agenda.

Figure 12 provides a visual synthesis of these relationships. The chart displays the number of links identified between each SDG and the 378 bioeconomy indicators analysed. The height of each bar represents the total number of associations per goal, while the colours within the bars indicate the qualitative nature of these relationships—ranging from strongly positive to more uncertain or potentially negative. This visualization makes it possible to quickly identify which SDGs are most strongly represented by bioeconomy indicators (for example, SDGs 2, 6, 8, 12, and 13) and which show more limited or ambiguous connections (such as SDGs 4, 5, and 16). Overall, the figure highlights both the scope and heterogeneity of the links between the

Figure 12: How bioeconomy indicators link to SDGs. Source. Own elaboration

4.5 Structure and functionalities

The monitoring tool is organised into two main modules: the **CBE Dashboard** and the **CBE Indicators**.

The **CBE Dashboard** brings together two complementary functionalities: the *benchmark analysis* and the *overview - mapping*. The first, which represents the main output of T2.3, enables users to conduct benchmark analyses across countries and over time. The second, the *overview - mapping*, provides interactive maps and scatterplots of selected indicators to deepen understanding and allow for visual exploration of country-level differences. This functionality is very similar to what the EU-BMS offers; however, since the benchmark analysis in SUSTRACK is based on normalised scores ranging from 1 to 6, we considered it essential to also provide access to the real values of the indicators within the same tool. This dual perspective enables users to better contextualise the insights obtained from the spider chart and interpret country performance more accurately. The reader can refer to section 4.6 for a practical example.

The **CBE Indicators**, in turn, function as a curated repository of circular bioeconomy indicators identified by the SUSTRACK team throughout the project. This repository not only offers access to a structured set of indicators but also facilitates exploration through filters and links to related information.

Figure 13 below shows the landing page of the SUSTRACK monitoring system. From this interface, users can access the different modules.

Figure 13: Landing page of the digital SUSTRACK monitoring system

The following sections provide a step-by-step user guidance on the main functionalities of the SUSTRACK monitoring tool.

4.5.1 CBE dashboard: Benchmark analysis

When the user clicks on **Benchmark analysis**, three key inputs must be selected (see Figure 14 Country-performance functionalities):

1. Countries
2. Years
3. Key area of interest

Clicking on each field opens a drop-down menu with the available options.

- For *Countries*, the user can select one or multiple countries from the EU27, including the EU27 average.
- For *Years*, the user can select any year between 2016 and 2023.
- For the *Key area of interest*, the user can choose among three thematic areas: *Environmental performance of the bio-based economy*, *Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs*, and *Sustainable and renewable resource use*. Each area contains a set of indicators relevant to the topic.

The tool allows comparisons either between countries in the same year or within a single country across years. While there is no hard limit to the number of selections, displaying too many at once can make the spider chart difficult to interpret. As a rule of thumb, we recommend selecting no more than four items (countries and/or years combined). For example, choosing two countries and one year will generate two lines in the spider chart. Adding one more country produces an additional line; while adding one more year doubles the number of lines (e.g., two countries and two years = four lines).

Once the desired options have been selected, the user should click *Update* to generate the results.

Figure 14: Example workflow - Country performance analysis

Figure 15 presents an example of results from the *Country Performance* analysis, in this case based on the selection of *Belgium* and *2021* as inputs.

The first output is a **spider chart**, which illustrates Belgium’s position in the chosen key area across a set of selected indicators. The scoring system is relative to the EU27 ranking:

- A score of **1** represents the lowest performance (bottom of the EU ranking).
- A score of **6** indicates the highest performance (top of the EU ranking, i.e., a leader).
- A score of **0** means that no data are available for that indicator.

This scoring approach ensures comparability across countries, as only indicators that can reasonably be expressed in relative terms have been included. Users interested in absolute values of indicators should refer to the *Cross-Country Analysis* module. In addition, only indicators with a clear interpretation of “good” or “bad” performance were included in the spider charts; indicators without a direct directional meaning were excluded. More detail on indicator selection is provided in the *Methods* chapter.

Below the spider chart Figure 15, the system shows how each indicator relates to the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**, highlighting potential synergies and trade-offs. A coloured legend accompanies each indicator:

- **Dark green:** a positive change in the indicator directly contributes to achieving the SDG.
- **Light green:** a positive change indirectly contributes to the SDG.
- **Dark red:** a positive change directly deteriorates progress on the SDG.
- **Light red:** a positive change indirectly deteriorates the SDG.

Further details on the classification of synergies and trade-offs with the SDGs can also be found in the *Methods* chapter.

Finally, users can access additional information on the indicator selection process and on the methodology applied in the benchmark analysis by clicking on the respective buttons: “Indicators selection?” and “Methodology?”. In both cases, a pop-up window will appear with a concise description of the underlying approach (Figure 16).

Figure 15: Type of results obtained by the country-performance analysis

Figure 16: Methodological notes on indicator selection and methodology used for benchmark analysis.

4.5.2 CBE dashboard: Cross-country analysis

The *Cross-country analysis* module provides a broader overview of trends across EU27 countries for a range of bioeconomy indicators, grouped into the three key areas of interest: **Environmental performance of the bio-based economy**, **Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs**, and **Sustainable and renewable resource use**.

This functionality is similar to the maps available in the EU-BMS, but here it is complemented with scatterplots. The addition of scatterplots allows users to explore the relationship between a selected indicator and other key explanatory variables. For example, biomass consumption is closely linked to the economic size or population of a country. The scatterplot, therefore, helps to assess whether relationships among variables are linear or follow other patterns.

When using the module, the user must first select the indicator and year of interest. The tool then automatically generates both a map and a scatterplot. For scatterplots, a default explanatory variable is pre-selected, but a drop-down menu offers alternative variables (commonly **population**, **GDP**, or **land surface**) to account for the scale effect of the indicator.

If the user wishes to focus on a specific country, they can select it to highlight its corresponding dot in the scatterplot. The maps use **quantile breaks** in the legend, while indicator units are displayed directly in the title of the figure. Both visualisations are interactive: the map allows zooming in and out, and hovering over a country displays the exact indicator value.

Figure 17 provides an example of the cross-country analysis workflow:

1. Select one of three key areas: Environmental performance of the bio-based economy, Bioeconomy competitiveness and jobs, and Sustainable and renewable resource use.
2. Select indicator: choose the bioeconomy indicator of interest from the drop-down list.
3. Select year: pick the year of analysis from the available range.

Review outputs: The tool automatically generates both a map and a scatterplot for the selected indicator and year.

- The **map** shows the distribution of the indicator across EU27 countries, with quantile-based legend classes. Users can zoom in/out and hover over a country to display exact values.
 - The **scatterplot** illustrates the relationship between the selected indicator and a default explanatory variable (e.g., GDP, population, land area).
4. Optional: users can choose an alternative explanatory variable from the drop-down menu.
 5. Optional: select a specific country to highlight its dot in the scatterplot for easier comparison.

Interpret results: the combined insights from the map (geographical distribution) and scatterplot (variable relationship) to better understand cross-country patterns.

Figure 17: Example workflow - Cross-country analysis

4.5.3 CBE indicators

The CBE Indicators module functions as a curated **repository** of bioeconomy-focused indicators. These indicators were identified through the literature review conducted in T2.1 and subsequently classified according to a dedicated taxonomy (see Table 6). In total, 574 indicators have been collected, spanning multiple sources such as the EU-BMS (particularly for national-level indicators), FADN⁵ (for regional-level indicators at NUTS 2 and NUTS 3), FAO, as well as insights from the SUSTRACK case studies carried out in WP3. The latter have been especially valuable for prioritising **product-level indicators**, which are included in the repository. Further details on these sector-specific indicators—covering construction, textiles, chemicals, and plastics—are provided in D3.3.

It is important to note that the CBE Indicators module does not host datasets per se (this would not be operationally feasible given resource constraints). Instead, it provides structured information on indicators, including, where available, references to the original data sources from which users can retrieve the underlying data.

The CBE Indicators module is organised into two main sections (Figure 18):

1. **User interface** - where users can apply filters to search for specific indicators.
2. **Indicators panel results** - where filtered indicators are displayed together with complementary information.

Figure 18: CBE indicators repository sections

User-interface

⁵ Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). Note that as of 2025, the Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN) is set to replace the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). The FSDN will build on the FADN's legacy, expanding its scope to cover not only farms' income and business activities but also information on their environmental and social sustainability performance.

Figure 19 shows the user-interface for searching indicators. Several approaches can be used (or a combination of them):

2. **Keywords:** by entering keywords into a dedicated search box (the indicator list updates automatically),

or by applying a series of filters. The available filters include:

3. **Indicator status:** existing / proposed.
4. **Implementation level:** EU, national, regional/cities, product/companies.
5. **Sustainability dimension:** environmental, social, economic, circularity, governance.
6. **Contribution to SDGs:** from Goal 1 to Goal 17.
7. **Societal goals** (as defined in the EU Bioeconomy Strategy):
 - SO1: Food and nutrition security
 - SO2: Managing natural resources sustainably
 - SO3: Reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources (whether sourced domestically or abroad)
 - SO4: Mitigating and adapting to climate change
 - SO5: Strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs

Finally, users can export the selected indicators (with complementary information according to the indicators taxonomy classification, when available) in Excel format through the “**Download Filtered Data**” button (7). Table 6 provides the full taxonomy used to classify indicators.

Download Filtered Data

Enter keywords to filter indicators

Indicator Status

Existing

Proposed

Implementation Level

EU National

Regions/Cities Product/Companies

Sustainability Dimensions

Environmental Economic

Social Circularity

Contribution to SDGs

#1 No poverty #2 Zero hunger

#3 Good health and well-being #4 Quality education

#5 Gender Equality #6 Clean water and sanitation

#7 Affordable and clean energy #8 Decent work and economic growth

#9 Industry, innovation, and infrastructure #10 Reduced inequalities

#11 Sustainable cities and communities #12 Responsible consumption and production

#13 Climate action #14 Life below water

#15 Life on land #16 Peace, justice, and strong institutions

#17 Partnerships for the goals

Societal Goals:

SO1 Food and nutrition security

SO2 Managing Natural Resources Sustainably

SO3 Reducing dependence on non-renewable unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad

SO4 Mitigating and adapting to climate change

SO5 Strengthening European Competitiveness and Creating Jobs

Figure 19: User-interface for indicators selection

Table 6: Full Taxonomy used to classify the indicator

Topic	Sub header	Classes & Categories	Detailed explanation
DATA	Basic info	UNIT:	The unit of measurement.
		Status of indicator (existing, proposed)	States whether the indicator is existing and mapped or a new proposed indicator.
		Availability of data	Is data available for the indicator and if so, to what degree; signal, indicator or potential? Signal refers to data being available, but only for a limited timeframe or geographic. Indicator refers to data being available and regularly updated. Potential refers to the potential of a meaningful indicator but there is no data available.
		Qualitative indicator	This class refers to indicators which do not involve enumeration, but instead are measured against pre-determined criteria.
		Quantitative indicator	This class refers to indicators which do involve enumeration.
	Coverage	Temporal	The timespan the indicator or signal has been active.
		Geographic	The geography the indicator, signal or potential is relevant for.
		Recent year	The most recent year for data collection.
LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION		EU	Indicators relevant for the EU level.
		National	Indicators relevant for the national level.
		Cities/regions	Indicators relevant for city/regional level (in particular municipal waste streams).
		Companies	Indicators relevant for company and industry level.
		Household	Indicators relevant for household level, particularly private consumption and initiatives at a citizens' level.
RATIONALE		Description of the indicator/signal/potential	Thorough description of the indicator/signal/potential. It is important that the description enables a common understanding.
METHOD		Methodical considerations	Relevant methodological flaws/limitations/weaknesses/blind spots as well as exceptional advantages related to the metric.
		Required methodology	The specific methodology required for this indicator, e.g. product LCA, PEF, material flow analysis, survey, etc.
AIMS	Sustainability pillars	Societal Goals	Societal goal addressed by the indicator
		Economic	Indicators that monitor progress related to economy aspects
		Environmental	Indicators that monitor progress related to environmental aspects
		Social	Indicators that monitor progress related to social aspects.
	Circularity	Circularity	Indicators that monitor progress related to circularity of resources
	Governance	Governance	Indicators that monitor governance aspects

CBE THEMES / SUB-THEMES	Primary production systems	Agriculture	
		Forestry	
		Aquaculture	
		Secondary production systems	
		Waste and circularity	
		Ecosystem conditions	
		Trade	
CBE AND SDGs	SDG 1: No poverty		
	SDG 2: Zero hunger		
	SDG 3: Good health and well being		
	SDG 4: Quality education		
	SDG 5: Gender equality		
	SDG 6: Clean water and sanitation		
	SDG 7: Affordable and clean energy		
	SDG 8: Decent work and economic growth		
	SDG 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure		
	SDG 10: Reduced inequalities		
	SDG 11: Sustainable cities and communities		
	SDG 12: Responsible consumption and production		
	SDG 13: Climate action		
	SDG 14: Life below water		
	SDG 15: Life on land		
	SDG 16: Peace, justice, and strong institutions		
	SDG 17: Partnerships for the goals		
VALUE CHAIN STEP	Primary sectors	Raw bio-based material extraction	
	Stock	Stock of resources (e.g., forestry)	
	Processing/Manufacturing services	Production	
	Users	Use phase	
	Disposal/Cascading/Recycling/Reusing	End of life	

		Whole chain	Whole chain
REFERENCES		Source	Name of organisation, title of journal article, or project from which indicator stems.
		Link to source	Link to the online reference for this indicator, if available.
		Link to data	Link to the data set for the indicator, if available.

Indicators panel results

On the right-hand side of the CBE Indicators module, the list of indicators automatically updates depending on the filters or keywords applied. Beyond the indicator name, complementary information is provided, such as the unit of measurement, implementation level, and sustainability dimension. The full taxonomy is presented in Table 6. Importantly, *Indicators panel results* also displays the **relationship between indicators and SDGs**, which is visualised through a heatmap (Figure 21), in a similar fashion to the spider chart described earlier. This allows users to explore synergies and potential trade-offs in a user-friendly manner.

INDICATOR	UNIT	Availability of data: Indicator/Signal/Potential	Boolean indicator	Recent year	Headline	Governance	Agriculture	Forestry	Acquaculture	Secondary production systems
1 Government support to agricultural research and development (by sector)	eur / inhabitant	Indicator		2020			x			
2 Daily calorie supply per capita by source	kcal/capita/d and %	Indicator		2018			X			
3 Food purchasing power	%	Indicator		2020			x		x	x
4 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population (yearly estimates)	%	Indicator		2019			x		x	x
5 Biomass directly consumed by EU citizens as food	1000 tonnes dry matter	Indicator		2018			x		x	x
6 Total biomass supply for food purposes, including inputs	1000 tonnes dry matter	Indicator		2018			x		x	x
7 Agricultural factor income per annual work unit	index (2010=100)	Indicator		2021			x			
8 Share of organic farming in utilised agricultural area	% of total utilised agricultural area (UAA)			2020			x			
9 Forest growing stock	1000m3			2020				x		
10 Surface of marine and terrestrial sites designated under NATURA 2000	% or km2 of land area			2020						

Figure 20: Indicators-panel results

Figure 21: indicators and relations with SDGs

4.6 Case study application: Spain

As part of the SUSTRACK DEPLOY conferences, interactive national workshops combining policy dialogue with capacity-building elements, the monitoring tool was used to provide participants with hands-on insights into their national context. In this line, each national workshop served as a tutorial for navigating the tool. The Spanish case study, presented below, illustrates how the SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment Tool can be applied in practice. A video tutorial of this exercise is also available at [<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kroDxg4E1WI>].

Step 1: Benchmarking progress over time

The first step consisted of exploring Spain’s environmental performance since the publication of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy in 2018. Using the **spider chart functionality** of the tool, participants compared 2017 and 2022 values of bioeconomy-related GHG emissions. The analysis revealed significant improvements in sectors such as fishing and aquaculture, forestry and logging, water exploitation, and paper and wood products (Figure 22). This temporal benchmarking allowed users to identify areas where Spain has successfully decoupled sectoral growth from environmental impact.

Figure 22: Benchmarking Spain’s progress on GHG emissions over time

Step 2: Benchmarking against the EU27

The tool was then used to situate Spain’s performance within the broader EU27 context. A second spider chart (Figure 23) compared Spain’s 2022 performance with the EU average. The results highlighted that, while Spain performs relatively well overall, important gaps remain in sectors such as paper and wood products, where emissions intensity is still above the EU27 benchmark. By contrast, Spain emerged as one of the best performers in the textile sector, ranking among the lowest in GHG emissions intensity.

Figure 23: Benchmarking Spain against the EU27

Step 3: Deep-dive analysis in a specific sector

To illustrate the flexibility of the tool, participants then focused on the textile sector. Using the map and scatterplot functionalities (Figure 24), the monitoring tool highlighted Spain’s relative importance in Europe’s textile industry. Spain is the **second largest producer** after Italy, followed by Germany and France. When benchmarking against these peers (Figure 25), Spain emerged as the most efficient in terms of GHG emissions per unit of output. This combination of scale and efficiency positions Spain as a leader in sustainable textile production.

Environmental performance of the bio-based economy (SO4)

Figure 24: Deep-dive analysis in textile sector

Figure 25: Benchmarking textile leaders in terms of GHG intensities

Step 4: Synthesis of insights

From 2017 to 2022, Spain achieved notable improvements in reducing GHG emissions in bioeconomy-related sectors such as fishing and aquaculture, forestry and logging, and water exploitation. These positive trends suggest the presence of effective sector-specific practices and policies, which could serve as reference points for other Member States. However, the benchmarking exercise also identified **hot spots** in paper and wood products, where performance lags behind the EU average. These findings invite a more detailed systems-thinking analysis to uncover underlying drivers—such as outdated production methods, weak enforcement of standards, or insufficient uptake of circular practices.

Conclusion

The Spanish case study illustrates how the SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment Tool can be used to generate practical insights into national performance across key bioeconomy-related sectors. Beyond the descriptive figures, the tool supports the formulation of policy-relevant questions, such as:

- How do countries perform across different dimensions of the circular bioeconomy (e.g., resource efficiency, innovation, environmental impact)?
- Where are the main strengths and weaknesses in a specific country?
- How does a country's performance compare to EU averages or peer countries?
- Which areas require targeted policy interventions to accelerate the transition towards a sustainable circular bioeconomy?

These guiding questions demonstrate the value of the tool in stimulating evidence-informed dialogue and prioritisation during policy workshops. However, it is important to underline its limitations. The monitoring tool does not provide a comprehensive or exhaustive analysis of the circular bioeconomy. Instead, it offers an accessible entry point for exploration, based on a set of

harmonised indicators and benchmarking functionalities. The insights should therefore be interpreted as indicative rather than conclusive, and always complemented with deeper sectoral studies, causal analyses, and stakeholder knowledge. In this sense, the tool is best understood as a starting point: it helps to contextualise performance, highlight areas of concern, and identify promising avenues for further investigation.

4.7 Technical specifications

The SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment Tool is a web application developed using R (R Core Team, 2023) 4.4.0 version, a free software environment particularly fit for statistical computing and data visualisation and widely used in many fields together with RStudio development environment. The scripts and materials described in the following sections, which constitute the tool, have been made publicly available in the GitHub account <https://github.com/SUSTRACK-Project/Tool>. GitHub is widely used cloud-based service for storing and sharing of source code. By storing the tool files there, we enable all kind of stakeholders to easily access and improve them.

4.7.1 Content

The application was developed using *Shiny*, a R package (Chang & et al., 2025) that enables the development and deployment of web applications in R and Python languages. The *Shiny* package is compatible with any other R package with exception of those that do not run on Ubuntu Linux and those that required access to the display.

Unlike many web applications that use different frontend and backend technologies, *Shiny* enables the straight-forward integration of both within an unique R-based framework, which can be easily defined in a single script commonly called *app.R* which shall at least contain three components (which may also be put in separated scripts):

- A *user interface* function (*ui*) comprehending the web interface including the front-end, i.e., everything users see and interact with in their browser
- A *server function* (*server*) comprehending the application back-end, i.e., all computational logic and application behaviour.
- A call to the *shinyApp* function

```
library(shiny)

ui <- ...

server <- ...

shinyApp(ui = ui, server = server)
```

Figure 26: Basic Shiny app components

However, this is the minimum required to develop an application and additional elements may be required for the application to fulfil its purpose. That is the case of the SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment tool, which development required the addition of a few elements to the default ones to enable the tool to perform all the foreseen tasks. Thus, the tool has a second script, *aux_functions.r*, that contains all the functions being used by the user interface and the server function so that the *app.r* script remains relatively easy to understand and work with. It also has three folders with information on tokens and secrets required to ensure safe deployment, images and colours to be used in the tools interfaced and again secrets to connect with the Google sheet where the number of visitors is being counted. In addition to this, the tool feeds on several .csv files containing:

- The indicator values to be displayed in the CBE Dashboard
- The information displayed in the CBE indicators
- The *directionality* of each indicator for the CBE Dashboard - Benchmarking graphs (see 4.5.1)
- Land use, total employment, total domestic material consumption and total GDP per country and year.

The data contained in these files comes from sources such as EUROSTAT, JRC or the UN Department of Economics and Social Affairs (see section 4.5).

Figure 27: SUSTRACK Monitoring & Assessment tool files

Finally, Shiny offers a number of functions to customize the user interface, however, since Shiny also uses Bootstrap (Sievert, 2025) HTML/CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) framework, it is possible to supplement the default function set with raw html code and CSS elements interwoven within the R scripts to better handle the design of the tool and thus enhance the tool user interface. This widget was extensively used within the *ui* function to manage colours, positions, sizes etc.

```
.box.box-primary {
background:#bac487;
text-align: center;}

.main-sidebar {
background-color: #d7e5c1;
width:16%;margin:0px;}
```

Figure 28: HTML/CSS code example

4.7.2 Infrastructure

The tool was deployed in a cloud server operated by Posit⁶ through *shinyapps.io*, a self-service platform built using Ubuntu Linux as the base operating system. *Shinyapps.io* offers a straightforward way to deploy, manage (e.g., capacity allocated, users access, etc) and monitor web applications directly from RStudio.

Figure 29: Shiny application infrastructure

Each application deployed through *shinyapps.io*, is self-contained, i.e., the actual application script, all the required R packages and their dependencies as well as the required data are put together in a *bundle* that would thus replicate the environment from the local machine where the application was developed. This way, the users do not need to have any of the R packages used

⁶ <https://posit.co/>

installed or any of the data accessible locally to use the application. The application will be then accessible through the URL `https://<account-name>.shinyapps.io/<application-name>/`

4.7.3 Scalability

The *shinyapps.io* free account establishes restrictions regarding the number of requests (users) the deployed web application can handle simultaneously, and the size of the bundle loaded (1GB). If an increase in the number of users or additional features that may make the application more complex is foreseen, it might be necessary to upgrade the account type to make sure Posit allocates enough capacity to support the app and deal with all the new requests. Besides larger files and capacity, paid accounts also offer other advantages such as customizing the URL to access the web application rather than using the default one.

4.7.4 Security

Through *shinyapps.io* each web application runs in its own protected environment or container and its URL is always served over a Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) encrypted connection. Further security layers, such as an authentication step, for instance, can be added with upgraded accounts.

To safely deploy the web application through shinyapps.io directly from the RStudio interface, the *rconnect* R package was used (Atkins, 2025). This package uses the token and secret automatically generated by the shinyapps.io account to safely access it and deploy the web application.

4.7.5 UI-Server Architecture

As any other Shiny web applications, the SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment tool frontend and backend consist of a number of components fulfilling different tasks. How these relate and communicate to each other constitutes the application architecture and is particular to each application, however, they all share some features. Among the components present in any Shiny application, *functions* may be among the most relevant ones, since they are responsible for performing all the tasks the tool shall be able to carry out. Other elements are *inputs* and *outputs* controls used to intake information and data to feed the functions and to put out the results generated by them. While *functions* clearly belong in the backend, *inputs* (numericInput, textInput, selectInput etc) and *outputs* (renderPlot, renderTable, renderText etc) controls move between the backend (where they are fed to functions or generated by them) and the frontend (where they are introduced by the users or displayed by the app).

Figure 30: Shiny application general architecture

In addition to these, and connecting the ui and server functions, Shiny offers a *reactive* system or layer which updates the app instantly whenever a user makes a change and thus renders it interactive. However, despite its obvious utility, reactivity is also a common source of bugs and bottlenecks, i.e., too much reactivity may slow down and even hamper the proper working of the app. For that reason, it is convenient to limit reactivity to what really needs to be updated.

Figure 31: Example of Shiny application architecture

In the SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment tool, the reactivity layer was used extensively to connect inputs, outputs and functions. It was however, implemented in the simplest way in most of the cases with just a data source (input) and an endpoint (output), with the exception of the check boxes used to filter the information to be displayed in the CBE Indicators table. In that case, the reactive layer also included conductors (reactive()).

Figure 32: Simplified version of SUSTRACK Monitoring and Assessment tool architecture

5 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

5.1 Ensuring a just and inclusive bioeconomy transition

The bioeconomy transition has the potential to drive sustainable development and economic growth. However, it also presents significant challenges for a just transition, particularly in ensuring gender equality and social inclusion. A just transition must be guided by key principles that promote fairness, participation, and equity:

- **Inclusive decision-making:** Decision-making processes should be inclusive and participatory, involving women and marginalised communities in the design and implementation of bioeconomy policies and programs.
- **Fair distribution of benefits and burdens:** The benefits and burdens of the bioeconomy should be distributed fairly, with women and marginalised communities having access to the benefits and being protected from the negative impacts.
- **Social protection:** Social protection measures, such as education and training programs, should be in place to support women and marginalised communities in adapting to the changes brought about by the bioeconomy transition.
- **Addressing historical inequalities:** The bioeconomy transition provides an opportunity to address historical inequalities and ensure that women and marginalised communities are empowered and included in the new economy.

Despite the importance of these aspects, data gaps hinder effective monitoring of social equity in the bioeconomy, limiting the ability to assess progress and ensure a truly just transition (Bianchi et al., 2024). Without gender-sensitive and inclusive data, inequalities may persist, preventing the fair distribution of bioeconomy benefits (Sanz-Hernández et al., 2022). In many cases, indicators capable of capturing gender, social or intersectional dimensions of bioeconomy dynamics are either inconsistently reported across countries or embedded within datasets that lack sufficient territorial or sectoral granularity. This challenge is compounded by the inherently multi-dimensional nature of the transition, where metrics on competitiveness or productivity, while critical, may obscure uneven social impacts if not explicitly disaggregated. Furthermore, certain aspects of governance and jobs & competitiveness indicators, explored in detail within this deliverable, highlight additional constraints. Governance structures designed to foster inclusive decision-making often vary substantially between regions, with some lacking formal mechanisms to ensure the systematic involvement of underrepresented groups. Similarly, while the assessment of employment and enterprise dynamics underscores the opportunities the bioeconomy offers for economic revitalisation, it also reveals risks of uneven benefits, particularly if emerging sectors do not integrate proactive policies to support gender balance or youth inclusion.

Recognising these challenges, in T2.3, we sought to **bridge part of this gap** by enhancing the SUSTRACK Monitoring System's capacity to capture social and governance dimensions of the bioeconomy. The work focused on **Competitiveness and Jobs**, following a structured approach that integrated literature review, cross-project comparisons, and a systematic evaluation of data availability. First, existing studies and European project deliverables, including outputs from BioGov.net, were analysed to identify relevant indicators capturing employment, skills development, inclusion of underrepresented groups, and governance participation. Candidate indicators were then compared against the current SUSTRACK Monitoring System to determine which were already captured, partially represented, or missing. This exercise, conducted in collaboration with internal partners, ensured that new suggestions were aligned with existing frameworks and feasible to implement.

Next, the project explored **publicly available, official EU data sources** (Eurostat, JRC DataM, CEDEFOP, FAO) to identify indicators that are measurable, reliable, and regularly updated. The focus was on simplicity, clarity, and cross-country comparability, ensuring that indicators could be used effectively for benchmarking and policy guidance. This process resulted in a set of **seven new candidate indicators**, including Labour Productivity in the Bioeconomy, Enterprise Birth Rate in Bioeconomy Sectors, Youth Employment Rate in Bioeconomy Sectors, Participation in Adult Learning in Bioeconomy, Gender Employment Gap in Bioeconomy, Employment Rate in High-Tech Sectors (as a proxy for high-skill bioeconomy employment), and R&D Personnel in Bioeconomy Sectors. Each indicator was carefully documented, detailing its definition, formula, unit, data source, and availability, and included in the CBE indicators repository of the SUSTRACK monitoring system.

Importantly, while **Labour Productivity** is already integrated into the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System, the other six indicators remain **for further investigation**. Their potential lies in providing more nuanced insight into the social and economic dimensions of the bioeconomy, complementing existing measures and helping to identify both opportunities and risks associated with the transition. Future work should focus on data collection for these indicators, enhancing their comparability, and exploring additional metrics to capture gender dynamics, social equity, and governance practices more comprehensively.

By closing data gaps and embedding gender-sensitive, intersectional perspectives throughout bioeconomy monitoring and policy design, the transition can become more inclusive, equitable, and firmly aligned with broader sustainability and social justice goals. This emphasis is not only integral to the fairness of the bioeconomy transition but also critical to its resilience and long-term legitimacy, ensuring that the path towards circular and bio-based systems does not replicate or exacerbate existing patterns of exclusion.

5.2 Environmental data from the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR)

Industrial emissions reporting under the **Industrial Emissions Directive 2010/75/EU** and the **European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register Regulation (EC) No 166/2006** provides a rich source of environmental data. This dataset contains information on the location and administrative characteristics of the largest industrial complexes in Europe, as well as releases and transfers of regulated substances to air, water, and soil. It also includes waste transfers reported under the E-PRTR and detailed data on energy input and emissions for large combustion plants (reported under IED Art. 72). E-PRTR covers the following sectors:

1. **Energy sector** - relevant due to bioenergy production and renewable energy integration.
2. Production and processing of metals
3. Mineral industry
4. **Chemical industry** - highly relevant but challenging due to limited guidance on the bio-based share of activities.
5. **Waste and wastewater management** - relevant for understanding recycling and biowaste valorisation.
6. **Paper and wood production and processing** - core bio-based industries.
7. **Intensive livestock production and aquaculture** - relevant for bio-based food production and by-products.
8. **Animal and vegetable products from the food and beverage sector** - directly linked to bioeconomy outputs.
9. Other activities

These datasets offer the potential to quantify environmental pressures from bio-based activities, providing complementary insights to traditional economic and material flow indicators. Within Sustrack, we conducted a tentative assignment of emissions from the chemical sector to bio-based activities based on consortium expertise as illustrated in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Assignment of emissions from chemical sector to bio-based activities

However, several limitations currently prevent full integration of these data into the Sustrack monitoring framework:

- **Normalisation challenges:** Emission intensities calculated from E-PRTR refer only to industrial activities obliged to report, which are not aligned with total sectoral outputs such as the gross value added (GVA) of the chemical industry.
- **Disentangling bio-based shares:** For many sectors, particularly the chemical industry, it remains difficult to reliably determine the extent of bio-based activity.

Despite these limitations, E-PRTR represents a promising data source for future work. Its high granularity enables detailed analyses of emissions by pollutant type and geolocation of facilities. Future research could focus on developing standardized approaches to estimate bio-based shares across sectors and normalizing emissions relative to economic or production indicators. Such efforts would enhance bioeconomy monitoring, providing spatially explicit assessment of environmental pressures across Europe.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The Sustrack monitoring system builds on the conceptual foundation of the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS) but translates it into a more operational and user-oriented framework. It combines a structured repository of over 500 indicators with an interactive online dashboard that allows users to perform benchmarking analyses across countries and thematic areas. The indicators are organised around three key dimensions – environmental performance, socio-economic dynamics, and resource management efficiency – and are linked to both the five EU bioeconomy societal objectives and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Through data visualisation, scoring, and cluster-based analyses, the system enables users to quickly identify strengths, weaknesses, and potential hotspots in national bioeconomy performance, providing a practical tool for evidence-based policy discussions and strategy development.

Looking ahead, the **SUSTRACK monitoring system** has strong potential for future exploitation. Thanks to its intuitive design and visual interface, it can serve as an accessible entry point for stimulating discussion within panels and working groups, particularly in countries taking their first steps toward developing a bioeconomy strategy or roadmap. In this sense, it can provide valuable support to those countries that do not yet have a dedicated monitoring system in place, helping them build initial capacities. Moreover, we expect that some of the SUSTRACK functionalities could serve as inspiration for the further development of the **EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS)**. As the EU-BMS represents the central reference for monitoring the bioeconomy at the European level, integrating features such as **benchmarking analyses** or **visual linkages between bioeconomy indicators and the SDGs** could significantly enhance its relevance, usability, and overall effectiveness.

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